

**Republic of Iraq
Ministry of Higher Education
And Scientific Research
Foundation of Technical Education
College of Health and Medical Technology \ Baghdad**

**ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNICABLE DISEASES
SURVEILLANCE SYSTEM ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY
HEALTH CARE CENTERS IN BAGHDAD
GOVERNORATE**

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE COLLEGE COUNCIL OF HEALTH AND MEDICAL
TECHNOLOGY AS A PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF
TECHNOLOGY IN COMMUNITY HEALTH AND
SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY**

**Submitted By
Jasim A. Khaleefah
B.Sc Community Health Technology / 2007**

**Supervised By
Dr. Sulaf A. Hussain
Assistant Professor**

March/2013 A.D

Jumada Al-awla / 1434 A.H

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Supervisor Certification

I certify that this thesis was prepared under my supervision as a partial requirement for the Degree of Master of Technology in Community Health Technology in the College of Health and Medical Technology.

Signature:

Name: **Dr. Sulaf A. Hussain**

Title: Assistant professor

Date: 15/4/2013

Linguistic certification

I certify that I have read this thesis entitled (**Assessment of Communicable Diseases Surveillance System Activities in Primary Health Care Centers in Baghdad Governorate**) by (**Jasim A. Khaleefah**), and I examined the language of the thesis and, my opinion, it is adequate as a thesis for the Degree of Master of Technology in Community Health Technology.

Signature:

Name: **Suha No'aman Rasheed**

Title: Assistant Professor

Date: 9/4/2013

In view of the available recommendations, I forward this thesis for debating by the examining committee.

Signature:

Name: **Dr. Basim Mosa Hassan**

Title: Lecturer

Head of Department

Date: 22/4/2013

Certification

We are the members of the examining committee; we certify that after reading this thesis (**Assessment of Communicable Diseases Surveillance System Activities in Primary Health Care Centers in Baghdad Governorate**) and examining the student (**Jasim A. Khaleefah**) in its contents. We think that it is adequate for the award of the Master Degree of Technology in Community Health Technology in the College of Health and Medical Technology.

Signature:
(Chairman)

Name: **Dr. Mazin Gh. Alrubaey**

Title: Professor

Date: 10 / 4 / 2013

Signature:
(Member)

Name: **Dr. Hassan M. Abdulhussein**

Title: Public Health Advisor

Date: 9 / 4 / 2013

Signature:
(Member)

Name: **Dr. Wafaa F. Tawfeeq**

Title: Assistant professor

Date: 9 / 4 / 2013

Signature:

(Member/Supervisor)

Name: **Dr. Sulaf A. Hussain**

Title: Assistant professor

Date: 15 / 4 / 2013

Signature:

Name: **Dr. Baqir Kareem Abed**

Title: Assistant Professor

The Dean

Date: 23 / 4 / 2013

1.1 Introduction:

Humanity faces many challenges that require global solutions. One of these challenges is the spread of communicable diseases that emerge or (re-emerge) from the interfaces between animals and humans and the ecosystems in which they live [1].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), communicable diseases account for more than 13 million deaths every year, including nearly two-thirds of all deaths among children under 5 years of age. Although the great majority of these deaths occur in developing countries, infectious diseases do not recognize international boundaries. They present a substantial threat to people in all parts of the world. In recent years, this threat has grown in volume and complexity. New diseases have emerged, others once viewed as declining in significance have resurged in importance, and many have developed substantial resistance to known antimicrobial drugs. This picture is complicated by the potential deployment of infectious disease pathogens as weapons of war or instruments of terror [2].

Effective communicable disease control relies on effective response systems and effective response systems rely on effective disease surveillance [3]. Health systems use the information from surveillance to plan, implement and evaluate health programmes and activities [4]. The overall aim of disease surveillance is to collect information for public health action [5].

Monitoring and evaluation is a vital component of communicable disease surveillance and response systems that helps to ensure that surveillance systems meet the objectives for which they were developed. Monitoring progress and evaluating outcomes and impact are critical in the development of core capacities for surveillance and response [6]. There should be ongoing evaluation of surveillance and assessment activities and

determination of training and capacity-building needs at all levels of the public health system. An evaluation process is needed that can be applied at all levels of the public health system [7].

Iraq has witnessed tremendous impacts on its health situation due to wars and sanctions, which have affected the infrastructure and led to more deterioration in providing of health services. Iraq has utilized primary health care system which has been applied since eighties [8].

Surveillance is the process of systematic collection, collation and analysis of data with prompt dissemination to those who need to know, for relevant action to be taken. A well-functioning disease surveillance system provides information for planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of public health intervention programmes. Surveillance for communicable diseases is a part of public health surveillance, which in turn is part of the wider health information system. The objective of the surveillance system and the use of the information determines the data collected and the speed of information flow within the system. Early warning of epidemics is essential for effective and rapid control, while information on endemic communicable disease is essential for monitoring the disease, either way, information on priority communicable diseases is critical for control. Many countries have developed surveillance capacities to monitor diseases with a high burden, to detect outbreaks of epidemic-prone disease and to monitor progress towards national or international control or eradication targets. In this sense, surveillance of communicable diseases is a national function [9].

1.2 Objectives of the Study:**1.2.1 General Objective:**

To improve the communicable diseases surveillance system in Baghdad.

1.2.2 Specific objective:

- Assess the core activities and supportive functions of the communicable diseases surveillance system in term of structure, performance, epidemic preparedness and response at all health facilities level in Baghdad.

2.1 Surveillance

Surveillance in the health field, the process of monitoring diseases as they occur. It is the “continuing scrutiny of all aspects of occurrence and spread of disease that are pertinent to effective control” [10].

Public health surveillance in some literature called epidemiological surveillance [11]. *Surveillance*; watching or monitoring, a procedure used instead of quarantine to control the spread of infectious disease, involving close supervision during the incubation period of possible contacts of individuals exposed to an infectious disease. Epidemiologic surveillance, the ongoing and systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of data about a disease or health condition, used in planning, implementing, and evaluating public health programs. It may be passive, requiring those parties responsible for reporting disease to do so on their own, or active, providing visits or other monitoring to those parties to ensure that information is obtained [12].

A public health surveillance system should disseminate health data effectively so that decision makers at all levels can understand the implications of the information. The audiences for these data can include public health practitioners, health care providers, members of affected communities, professional and voluntary organizations, policy makers, the press, and the general public [13].

The nature of surveillance is practical and it is important that information gained from data analysis be linked to public health decisions and actions. In other words, only data that will be used should be collected. To be most effective, a surveillance system must be able to collect, manage and report data in a consistent, clear and timely manner [14]. A surveillance information system should, thus, not be a static entity but a process whereby health-related data is gathered, shared, analyzed, and used for decision-making in health [15]. Health systems use the information

from surveillance to plan, implement and evaluate health programmes and activities. An effective surveillance system has the following tasks:

- to find diseases which cause significant morbidity or mortality, and that can be controlled;
- to identify and correctly classify diseases;
- to correctly reflect the distribution of diseases over time, place and persons;
- to clearly define the diseases under surveillance;
- To set out effective methods for data collection, analysis, interpretation and feedback of information [4].
- To determine appropriate action plans based on the data processed in the system [16].

Surveillance data should be collected, analyzed and interpreted. Public health authorities should be informed to allow them to take appropriate action. In most surveillance systems, information is collected at the local level and sent to regional and national health authorities, which compile and analyze the data. The results of the data analyses are then summarized in reports that are provided to the national and local health authorities. In some countries, these reports are also made available to the public and to international agencies, such as WHO and nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) [17]. The collection of surveillance data generally involves sending data from the most peripheral level to more central levels [18].

Health surveillance activities in any country are conducted within the context of social factors—such as age distribution, gender issues, lifestyle, cultural background and socioeconomic status, which may or may not be stable. Surveillance systems in developing countries are susceptible to shortcomings [19], So data collectors must understand the purpose of the surveillance system, be committed to its goals and see evidence that the information is used to improve public health [17].

The purposes of disease surveillance are to:

- Identify, investigate and help control outbreaks or epidemics.
- Identify specific population groups at high risk of illness or death from priority diseases.
- Evaluate the impact of preventive and curative control activities on the incidence and prevalence of priority diseases in the community.
- Confirm current priorities among disease control activities.
- Motivate health workers (feedback, supervision, follow-up).
- Maintain support of government and partner agencies [20].
- Monitor trends (determine the distribution and spread of the disease over time) [21].

2.1.1 Surveillance Functions

The six universal surveillance functions as shown in (Figure 2.1) are carried out at various administrative levels, depending on the size, resources and infrastructure of the country concerned and the characteristics of the health event [22].

Figure 2.1: The six universal functions of surveillance [23]

2.1.2 Attributes of Effective Disease Surveillance:

Simple and efficient

Simplicity refers to the ease of operation of the system as a whole and each of its components (case definition, reporting procedures, etc.). In general, a surveillance system should be as simple as possible while still meeting its objectives [24].

Flexible

Refers to the ability of the method used for surveillance to accommodate changes in operating conditions or information needs with little additional cost in time, personnel, or funds [25].

Complete

Effective disease surveillance is complete. That is, reports are received and screened from all reporting units.

Timely

Effective disease surveillance provides information when it is due.

Useful

Effective disease surveillance collects useful information to show disease trends, detect epidemics, estimate the magnitude of a disease, stimulate research, which likely leads to control or preventive measures, identify risk factors, assess the effectiveness of the control measures, or promote and improve clinical practice.

Representative

Effective disease surveillance accurately describes the frequency of a disease, its geographical distribution, and the population affected.

Hierarchical

In an effective surveillance system, the data flows in a hierarchical manner from the most peripheral level to the most central level. In this way, health officers at each level receive data about the area under their jurisdiction,

which can be analyzed and used to guide local disease control activities [20].

These attributes should be assessed when evaluating a surveillance system [26].

2.2 Communicable Disease Surveillance

Surveillance of communicable diseases is a public health corner stone. Routine notification data on communicable diseases are used as a basis for public health action as well as for policymaking [5]. Surveillance systems must detect new communicable diseases as well as recognize and track diseases that currently are, or have the potential to become, of major public health importance [27].

Surveillance of disease, in communicable disease control, surveillance consists in the process of systematic collection, orderly consolidation, analysis and evaluation of pertinent data with prompt dissemination of the results to those who need to know, particularly those who are in a position to take action.

It includes the systematic collection and evaluation of ;

- 1) Morbidity and mortality reports.
- 2) Special reports of field investigations of epidemics and of individual cases.
- 3) Isolation and identification of infectious agents by laboratories;
- 4) Data concerning the availability, use and untoward effects of vaccines and toxoids, immunoglobulin's, insecticides and other substances used in control.
- 5) Information regarding immunity levels in segments of the population.
- 6) Other relevant epidemiological data [14].

surveillance is the first level of defense to the global threat from epidemic diseases, and explained that the determinant for success in response depends on the capacity at global and national level [6].

Many countries have developed surveillance activities for communicable diseases in order to monitor diseases with a high burden, detect outbreaks of epidemic-prone disease and monitor progress towards national or international control / eradication targets. In this sense, surveillance of communicable diseases is a national function; and the sum of all surveillance activities represents the "national communicable disease surveillance system" [28].

Surveillance for infectious diseases is quite complex, requiring the notification data to be collected, entered in a database, cleaned, referred to investigators, summarized and reported [29].

Data obtained through infectious disease surveillance are used to:

- 1) Measure the burden of disease.
- 2) Monitor disease trends.
- 3) Detect infectious disease outbreaks and unusual disease events.
- 4) Direct immediate public health action.
- 5) Assess the impact of control and prevention measures.
- 6) Support planning and policy efforts.
- 7) Prioritize the allocation of public health resources.
- 8) Provide a basis for epidemiologic studies [30].

Communicable disease surveillance, forecasting and response focused on strengthening national early warning, surveillance, epidemic preparedness and response systems, in accordance with the International Health Regulations 2005 (IHR) [31]. Surveillance for illnesses that require

the prompt treatment of close contacts is one of the most important activities of local health departments [32].

Effective infectious disease surveillance will “contribute to” an effective control of the disease. An effective surveillance system needs to have standards in terminology, reporting formats and methods in order to ensure quality of the surveillance system and to enable easier/consumer friendly participation by those involved [33]. Disease surveillance ought to be an important component of public health programme in every country [34].

2.3 Establishing Surveillance System

Reasons for conducting public health surveillance can include the need to assess the health status of a population, establish public health priorities, and reduce the burden of disease in a population by appropriately targeting effective disease prevention and control activities [35]. Surveillance systems are established for the identification of specific outcomes, such as a disease or injury, or for risk factors, and must have clearly expressed goals. Explicit case definitions are essential for a useful surveillance system. The initiation and maintenance of any successful surveillance system will reflect recognition of the human element in surveillance practice in data collection, analysis, and data dissemination. Attention to the people involved in such a system will increase its use [11].

Different countries have different epidemics, different surveillance systems and different data use needs. It is hoped, however, that all countries can find some general principles that will provide pointers on how to improve performance in areas of data use relevant to them [36]. Since surveillance is a fluid process, as populations or health problems change, the surveillance system must adapt [37].

Many challenges were confronted in the planning and implementation of the surveillance system [38]. Building surveillance and response capabilities should be a priority for the containment of known epidemic-prone infections, emerging infectious risks and unexpected disease threats, including those that may be deliberately initiated, through global epidemic intelligence and global outbreak alert and response [39]. When setting up surveillance systems, it is important to be aware of the local distribution of health conditions and include these in the surveillance programme [40]. Health authorities support the surveillance and response system by providing training, supervision and resources [41]. The overall goal of these surveillance activities is to contribute for reducing the incidence and prevalence of communicable diseases [42].

At the beginning, it is important to understand clearly the purpose of establishing or maintaining a surveillance program. This includes a determination of priority health events for surveillance, which surveillance data elements are necessary, and how and when they are to be used. The usefulness of surveillance activities can be increased by early attention to the components of establishing a public health surveillance system (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Elements in establishing a surveillance system [11]

However, enhanced surveillance capacity cannot yet be deployed in all or even in those countries with hotspots, because most have generally poor or inadequate public and animal health services and deficient regulatory controls. Therefore, capacity building for basic human and animal health services and the establishment of sustainable surveillance capacity in countries and internationally will be a major long-term priority [1].

The country plan or policy for the surveillance system should include minimum standards at each administrative level [23]. Most surveillance systems have a central level, intermediate levels and a level of point-of-contact with the health event, which may include health facilities, laboratories, and rehabilitation institutes and community centers [22].

Countries may have two intermediate levels (e.g. district and region). This will depend on the size of the country and the structure and level of development of the health service. In many cases, the professional at this level will have other tasks in the area of programme management. The tasks must be manageable and the surveillance data be perceived as immediately useful. In some cases, it may be more appropriate that the task of outbreak investigation be undertaken from the central level [28]. As in figure 2.3;

Figure 2.3: Information Flow in Communicable Disease Surveillance

2.4 Setting Priorities

Surveillance priorities should be appropriate to the disease epidemiology, infrastructure and resources in each country [28]. All countries should review their list of priority diseases for surveillance periodically to see if it reflects current needs. Prioritization only makes sense if it happens within the right context; political endorsement of the

process and willingness to accept the results of the exercise are prerequisites [43]. One of the important components of the national surveillance plan is a list of priority diseases for surveillance. This list, as short as possible, should be established with the close participation of national health authorities. Surveillance priorities should be appropriate to the disease epidemiology, infrastructure and resources in each country. National surveillance systems should reflect global goals for communicable disease control as stated in the WHO 9th Global Programme of Work and be in line with regional surveillance plans defined by WHO Regional Offices. Once priority diseases have been selected and the gaps identified, a plan of action for surveillance should be developed. An integrated approach, which aims to coordinate and streamline all surveillance activities, is advised. To this end a central body, which may be based in the Ministry of Health, should coordinate all the surveillance activities [28].

2.4.1 Priority Diseases by WHO

The list of priority diseases may vary from country to country depending on the local epidemiological situation, needs and health system. Countries are encouraged to keep the list to the minimum possible to ensure that adequate resources are available to carry out a response and the list is manageable by the system [44]. The priority diseases in the African and Eastern Mediterranean Regions include:

- Diseases to be eradicated: poliomyelitis and Dracunculosis;
- Diseases to be eliminated: leprosy, neonatal tetanus, and trachoma;
- Epidemic prone diseases: meningitis, measles, cholera, yellow fever, shigellosis;
- Diseases of major public health importance: malaria, HIV/AIDS/STIs, Tuberculosis, Onchocerciasis, Schistosomiasis, hepatitis B and Trypanosomiasis [45].

2.4.2 Priority Diseases in Iraq

Priority national public health diseases and/or could cause outbreaks in Iraq, including:

- TB
- Typhoid
- Hepatitis
- Cholera
- Malaria
- Leishmaniasis
- Schistosomiasis
- Meningitis
- HIV/AIDS and STIs [46].

2.5 Reporting of Communicable Diseases

One of the mainstays of communicable disease surveillance is the reporting and confirmation of cases seen in health facilities [27]. Reporting of some communicable diseases is required within countries and in some instances internationally to WHO. Reporting can take the form of either a case report or an outbreak report.

1. **Case reports:** Case reporting provides diagnosis, age, sex and date of onset for each person with the disease. Sometimes it includes identifying information such as the name and address of the person with the disease. Additional information such as treatment provided and its duration are required for certain case reports.
2. **Outbreak reports:** Outbreak reporting provides information about an increase above the expected number of persons with a communicable disease that may be of public concern. The specific disease may not be included in the list of diseases officially reportable, or it may be of unknown etiology if it is newly recognized or emerging [47].

Most countries have laid down regulations for the reporting of infectious diseases [48]. In most countries, notifiable disease surveillance systems rely on mandatory reporting of cases by physicians and laboratories [49]. Notifiable disease (ND) reporting systems provide the basis, for surveillance of communicable diseases in most states [50]. In general, mandatory notification systems are not very reliable, their performances depending on the country and/or the disease [51]. In addition, they need to be tailored to the public health objectives and health systems of each country [52].

The reporting of a case should be timely and need not be delayed until all epidemiologic data are available. Such data may be reported later and added to the original case report centrally. While district health authorities are encouraged to collect all information requested by the reporting system, when some items are not available the case should be reported with missing items listed as unknown. A case should never go unreported or deleted because of missing data. The only exception is when data to be determined whether the case meets the case definition are missing. Such cases should not be reported [33]. For effective containment of outbreaks, patients with infectious diseases of public health importance must be recognized and promptly reported to those responsible for prevention and control activities [53].

Incomplete reporting is inherent to any passive surveillance system. Knowledge and awareness of current reporting rules, willingness to comply, severity of the disease, available diagnostic tests, age of the patient, confidentiality issues surrounding the disease, changes in the case definitions over time, and access to or availability of health care services all may influence the likelihood of reporting [54]. Where communities are engaged in the surveillance system, case definitions are not required and open reporting of unusual/unexpected events should be encouraged [14].

Regular bulletins are often used to disseminate health information however; these can vary in quality and usefulness [55].

The list of nationally reportable infectious diseases changes periodically. Diseases may be added to the list as new pathogens emerge or deleted as their incidence declines. As knowledge increases and diagnostic technology improves, some definitions will change to reflect those trends [56].

The essential means of notification:

- 1) Telephone.
- 2) E-mail.
- 3) Fax.
- 4) By persons [57].

2.6 Feed-Forward and Feedback

Feedback is an essential component of surveillance. Feedback is critical for two reasons:

1. It motivates people to continue sending data since they can see that their data are used.
2. The quality of the data is likely to be better because the reports may show errors that are obvious to those who supplied the data, and can therefore be corrected [58].

Monthly or quarterly feedback of surveillance information to senior management, health staff, and other concerned parties is critical to establish effective surveillance. Providing feedback information to all designated reporting sites is necessary to:

- 1) Report progress and problems.
- 2) Verify that data are correct.
- 3) Motivate health agents.
- 4) Compare states, provinces, and districts.
- 5) Exchange ideas [20].

Feedback also raises awareness about certain diseases and any achievements of disease control and prevention activities in the area. Feedback should be regular and timely at all levels of the health delivery system. Feedback can be verbal, as in a telephone call, staff meeting, or supervisory visit; or it can be written, as in a report, fact sheet, or bulletin [59].

The term feed-forward refers to the process by which data are supplied by one level to the next, more central, level. It is the responsibility of each level to ensure that the more central level is kept informed about the condition under surveillance. Feed-forward is no less an important part of surveillance. The more peripheral level has a responsibility to keep the more central level informed of the disease under surveillance. Each level has its role to play in the whole process of surveillance - whether it is to detect and investigate cases or to provide guidance and support – and should therefore know what is happening [58]. In today's world, feedback of surveillance data to health care providers has already been shown to improve performance [60].

2.7 Communications and Technologies

The arrival of electronic tools in all countries has already changed surveillance activities, going in the direction of integrated multi-disease surveillance. Electronic reporting of surveillance data is increasingly common, initially using diskettes and now using web-based reporting mechanisms. Thanks to electronic databases, data can be analyzed more easily and rapidly and when geographical information is available, they can be linked to geographical information systems (GIS). The dissemination of surveillance data and their presentation to a wider audience, as well as internal feedback, are now also achieved through dedicated websites and

compact disks [3]. The capability of computers and technology creates great opportunity for surveillance activities [61].

The backbone of any plan or response is always the ability to communicate. Communications take many forms, and must function within many diverse environments. A wide range of information, from audio and video data to laboratory results to feedback from remote monitors and sensors to Internet data, will all need to make use of the communications backbone [62].

Enhanced telecommunication technologies within and outside health care facilities can facilitate greater access to health care data [63]. Mobile and uniform health care data should facilitate increased and easier communication of preexisting conditions, procedures, previous laboratory results, and others among health care facilities [64]. Low cost and low-tech communications systems are often the most practical and effective during such difficult circumstances. Megaphones, car battery-operated public address systems, community radio (also powered by battery or generators) are good ways to quickly disseminate messages to affected families and communities [65].

These new health information technologies and the Internet are important drivers affecting the future directions of global surveillance communications, particularly facilitating the collection and transmission of information at speeds that allow for better emergency preparedness and response [66]. Develop mechanisms for networking and regular feedback of surveillance data to all sectors contributing to disease surveillance (primary health care providers, hospital-based clinical services, laboratories, environmental, animal health, food safety experts and others) as well as culturally appropriate feedback to communities about trends in their burden of emerging diseases [67].

2.8 Epidemiological Investigation

The purpose of investigating a communicable disease epidemic is to identify its cause and the best means to control it [68]. The following (10) steps are essential considerations in every epidemiological investigation. It is this list to which practicing epidemiologists return more than any other:

- 1) Confirm the diagnosis [70].
- 2) Determine the existence of an epidemic.
- 3) Propose measures for control and prevention.
- 4) Define and count the cases.
- 5) Orient the data in terms of time, place, and person.
- 6) Determine who is at risk of having the health problem.
- 7) Develop and test an explanatory hypothesis.
- 8) Compare the hypothesis with the proven facts.
- 9) Plan a more systematic study.
- 10) Prepare a written report [69].

Public health surveillance and epidemiological investigation is the ability to create, maintain, support, and strengthen routine surveillance and detection systems and epidemiological investigation processes, as well as to expand these systems and processes in response to incidents of public health significance [71].

2.8.1 Role of Field Epidemiologists in Providing Evidence

In many countries, a shortage of trained epidemiologists has been aggravated by rapid turnover and migration of trained health personnel to other countries. Field epidemiology training programmes have greatly assisted in human resources development, appropriate outbreak investigation and improvement of communicable disease surveillance [39]. It is crucial that the personnel involved in surveillance activities be trained for their surveillance tasks, and there is a need for ongoing in-service

training at all levels, e.g., through workshops followed by close supervision in the field [28].

2.8.2 Role of Laboratory Support in Disease Surveillance

Laboratories play an important role in disease surveillance. They help in early detection of outbreaks, confirmation of etiology, tracing the spread of infection, detection of carriers, detection of new agents, and monitoring drug resistance. They help in identifying early warning signals and confirm the end of outbreaks. For the laboratories to function effectively in surveillance it is essential to have rapid systematic sampling, transportation and testing of samples from suspected cases. The time for confirmation should be restricted to the minimum to avoid delay in specific public health action [72].

2.8.3 Case Confirmation

Case/outbreak confirmation refers to the epidemiological and laboratory capacity for confirmation. Capacity for case confirmation is enhanced through improved referral systems, networking and partnerships. This means having the capacity for appropriate specimen collection, packaging and transportation. The existence of internal and external quality control mechanisms are important elements for case confirmation, which help to ensure the validity and reliability of test results [73].

A confirmed case generally refers to a patient presented with compatible clinical features and the laboratory studies fulfill one or more of the laboratory confirmation criteria listed for the condition. Some cases may be classified as “deleted” if investigation revealed that the epidemiological, clinical and/or laboratory findings do not meet the surveillance case definition. Such cases will be excluded in the trend analysis. The status of any reported cases may be updated based on the latest available evidence collected during the investigations [74].

2.8.4 Epidemic Thresholds

Knowledge of epidemic thresholds of priority diseases is essential for health personnel to recognize and respond to an epidemic [75]. The term epidemic threshold refers to the level of disease above which an urgent response is required. The threshold is specific to each disease and depends on the infectiousness, other determinants of transmission and local endemicity levels. For certain diseases, such as cholera or haemorrhagic fever, one case is sufficient to initiate a response. For other diseases, such as malaria, establishing a threshold ideally requires the collection of incidence data over a period of months or years. Two thresholds are recommended to guide different sets of activities, depending on the phase of development of an outbreak:

The *alert threshold* is used to: (a) sound an early warning and launch an investigation at the start of an outbreak; (b) check epidemic preparedness; (c) start a vaccination campaign if there is an outbreak in a neighboring area; and (d) prioritize areas for vaccination campaigns in the course of an outbreak. The *epidemic threshold* is used to confirm the emergence of an outbreak so as to step up control measures, e.g. mass vaccination and appropriate case management. The epidemic threshold depends on the context, and when the risk of an outbreak is high, a lower threshold, more effective in this situation, is recommended [76]. Table (2.1) gives samples of some diseases threshold.

Table 2.1: Sample of Some Diseases Threshold [76]

SAMPLE ALERT THRESHOLDS (may need to be adapted for particular context)	
Acute watery diarrhoea:	5 cases in the 5 years and over age group
Bloody diarrhoea:	5 cases
Measles:	1 case
Meningitis – suspected:	5 cases or 1.5 times the baseline
Acute haemorrhagic fever syndrome:	1 case
Acute jaundice syndrome:	5 cases or 1.5 times the baseline
Malaria:	5 cases or 1.5 times the baseline
Acute flaccid paralysis (suspected poliomyelitis):	1 case
Neonatal tetanus:	1 case
Fever of unknown origin:	1.5 times the baseline
Other communicable diseases:	1.5 times the baseline
Unknown disease occurring as a cluster:	report any cluster
Severe malnutrition:	2 cases
Baseline = average weekly number of cases of the disease calculated over the past 3 weeks.	

Epidemiological surveillance provides data about incidence of disease in the community that can help raise or lower the threshold of clinical suspicion for a particular infectious disease, encouraging early detection and appropriate treatment [77]. For detecting epidemics, a surveillance system should allow public health officials immediate access to new information [78].

2.8.5 Outbreak Investigation

An outbreak investigation involves determining the cause of an outbreak and who is at risk, so that control measures can be implemented, thus reducing morbidity and mortality. It should begin as soon as an alert detected by surveillance has been verified [79]. Suspected disease outbreaks, indicated by information from a health surveillance system, should be rapidly investigated using standards protocols for assessment. The assessment should enable decisions to be taken on how to control the outbreak [80].

Good information is part of good case management, and health care workers need to be trained in collecting basic information even when there is no outbreak. A case definition must be agreed and made widely known before the outbreak [81].

2.8.6 Outbreak Response

The term ‘outbreak’ is generally used when the number of cases observed is greater than the number normally expected in a given geographical area during a given period. However, the definition can vary depending on the nature of the disease and the disease control objectives. When an increase in the number of cases is observed, you should determine whether the increase could be termed an ‘outbreak’ or an expected trend, for example by season. As an outbreak can trigger a previously determined set of activities [82]. Outbreak detection is a key function of surveillance. An outbreak is an increase in the occurrence of cases of a disease above the baseline number. However, for some diseases, just one or two cases occurring in areas where they typically do not occur may constitute an outbreak [83].

The response to communicable disease events consists of intervention activities to control the outbreak event. These intervention activities can be preceded by an investigation and research phase if little or nothing is known about the aetiology and the impact of the event [84]. A disease or an event under surveillance is first picked up by the health care system, which reports it to the public health authority for interpretation and initiating action [85].

Several countries presented their experiences in detection and response to epidemiological emergencies. Many of them using syndromic surveillance as a framework for early detection of etiologic agents. This type of surveillance has helped to improve sensitivity in the detection of diseases and etiological diagnosis in several countries [86].

2.9 Weaknesses in Developing Countries Surveillance Systems

Weaknesses in developing countries systems reduce the ability of public health authorities at every level to understand and control infectious disease threats. These shortcomings limit the success of ambitious international programs such as the polio eradication effort, and impair the routine surveillance of other diseases and the identification and control of outbreaks, newly emerging diseases, and antimicrobial resistance. Surveillance systems in all countries suffer from a number of common constraints. However, these constraints have their greatest impact in the poorest countries, where per capita expenditure on all aspects of health care amounts to only about 3 % of expenditure in high-income countries. Surveillance in developing countries is often impaired by shortages of human and material resources [2]. In most developing countries, surveillance systems are often weak or have developed in an uneven fashion, with various surveillance activities funded and managed by different control programmes or organizations resulting in duplication of efforts and inefficient use of resources and systems [87]. A major weakness remains the lack of financial resources, particularly to address laboratory capacity strengthening. The need for improved communication systems was also highlighted [88].

Despite increased interest in strengthening health systems for developing countries, the current reality is that the health systems in most developing countries fall short of the requirements to implement the goals suggested by the World Health Organization (WHO) International Health Regulations (2005) [89].

Developed countries have constructed their public health and disease control strategies by using the principles of field epidemiology. Developing countries need to build and sustain human capacity in field epidemiology [90]. Most traditional global disease surveillance programmes target

specific diseases; infrastructure and support are relatively weak for the more difficult task of tracking emerging and re-emerging diseases. This is particularly true in developing countries, where scarce human and material resources may not support even routine surveillance tasks [91].

Today, an increasing number of private sector foundations with a public health focus are funding disease surveillance programs in limited resource settings [92]. Such enhanced support can greatly assist in sustaining the core capacities and competencies necessary for successful regional surveillance networks. Public-private partnerships for infectious disease surveillance are becoming increasingly common [93]. If systemic changes are made but not sustained, improvements will be lost and the system will either revert to its prior state or perhaps get worse [94].

2.10 Assessment of Communicable Diseases Surveillance

Assessment: Is a systematic or non-systematic way of gathering relevant information, analyzing and making judgment on the basis of the available information [74].

Each country needs to periodically assess its overall surveillance system so that this continues to reflect national disease control priorities, improves efficiency and takes advantages of new methods and techniques to strengthen surveillance [43]. Reviewing surveillance systems for infectious diseases also has the potential to identify worthwhile improvements to the organization of such systems at a country level. It may also identify gaps in these systems and whether or not important diseases, hazards, determinants, and interventions are under surveillance at all [95].

Any assessment should aim to develop or update a national plan for communicable disease surveillance so that the national surveillance and response system is improved overall. In a given country, it should bring

together all those who have responsibility for surveillance of communicable diseases and assess systematically the national surveillance activities as one system [3]. The description of the surveillance system should include objectives, case definitions, and the specific components of data collection, analysis, and dissemination. Most important, the actions that will be taken and the results expected based on the data from the surveillance system should be included. Surveillance data are used to assess control activities programs [11]. Data from public health surveillance systems should be assessed regularly if they are to retain their utility for public health workers [96].

The purpose of evaluating public health surveillance systems is to ensure that problems of public health importance are being monitored efficiently and effectively. Public health surveillance systems should be evaluated periodically, and the evaluation should include recommendations for improving quality, efficiency, and usefulness [97]. Assessing the current surveillance and action activities in the first step is knowing what and how surveillance and action activities are being performed. The assessment of surveillance and action activities involves asking several questions about the system and its performance [95]. Surveillance outcomes should stimulate policy development and research by identifying issues requiring action or further information needs [98].

2.10.1 Monitoring and Evaluation

Any surveillance activity that is implemented must be evaluated regularly to ensure that it is meeting its objectives [99]. As in all surveillance systems, routine monitoring and evaluation plays a critical role in ensuring that the system is functioning effectively and can adapt over time to changing systems and environments. At a minimum, routine monitoring of system performance and regular wider system evaluations

should be undertaken. The routine monitoring and evaluation may include the following areas:

2.10.1.1 Routine monitoring

- Number of outbreaks detected compared to other reporting systems.
- Accuracy and timeliness of information sources from initial event report.
- Time from notification to response.

2.10.1.2 Regular evaluations

-At least two events per year are evaluated from notification to confirmation, assessment and response. At each stage, the performance of the system should be evaluated [14].

Monitoring and evaluation is a vital component of communicable disease surveillance and response systems that helps to ensure that surveillance systems meet the objectives for which they were developed [6]. There should be ongoing evaluation of surveillance and assessment activities and determination of training and capacity-building needs at all levels of the public health system. An evaluation process is needed that can be applied at all levels of the public health system [7]. It is not sufficient to implement what appear to be viable surveillance systems, without ongoing monitoring [100].

2.10.2 Core and Support functions of surveillance systems

The core and support functions of surveillance systems to be assessed are:

2.10.2.1 Core functions

- 1) Case detection.
- 2) Case registration.
- 3) Case confirmation.
- 4) Reporting.
- 5) Data analysis and interpretation.
- 6) Epidemic preparedness.
- 7) Response and control.

- 8) Feedback.

2.10.2.2 Support functions

- 1) Standards and guidelines.
- 2) Training.
- 3) Supervision.
- 4) Communication facilities.
- 5) Resources.
- 6) Monitoring and evaluation.
- 7) Coordination [74].

2.11 Communicable Diseases

Infectious disease, a disease caused by a specific infectious agent or its toxic products that arises through transmission of that agent or its products from an infected person, animal, or reservoir to a susceptible host [101]. The field of infectious diseases, or more accurately the importance of illness due to infections, played a major role in the development of epidemiological research in the 19th and early 20th centuries [102]. The growing importance of these diseases is undisputed [103].

Infectious diseases present the most important acute problems in all countries and a major disease burden in developing countries [70]. Every year communicable diseases kill more than 13-14 million people throughout the world [104] although the great majority of these deaths occur in developing countries [105]. In these countries, approximately 46% of all deaths are due to communicable diseases, and 90% of these deaths are attributed to acute diarrhoeal and respiratory infections of children, AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria, and measles [47]. Infectious diseases cause 63% of all childhood deaths and 48% of premature deaths. Many of these deaths are caused by epidemic infectious diseases such as cholera, meningococcal disease, and measles [27].

It is not always possible to identify people who may spread infection to others, therefore; standard precautions to prevent the spread of infection must be followed at all times [106]. The most vulnerable groups—children, pregnant and lactating mothers, the elderly, and low income groups, particularly the underprivileged in urban areas—are the ones whose survival and development are threatened most by the slow recovery of health services [107]. Adequate preparation and response planning for epidemic outbreaks are crucial, particularly given the unavailability of vaccines and immunization supplies in health structures [108]. Infection Prevention and Control (IPC) policies and technical guidelines should be determined at the national level and adapted for local implementation. It is important to acknowledge that IPC measures applied during an outbreak should be built on a solid foundation of good daily practice [109].

2.11.1 Infectious Diseases Control

Infectious diseases control depends on broad extrinsic factors such as socio-economic stability, and accessibility and acceptability by the populations of the health services [110]. The appropriate control and management for a particular disease in a population, depends on the burden of that disease in the population. The levels of disease occurrence in a population are described as endemic, sporadic, epidemic or outbreak, or pandemic. An endemic disease is present in a specified geographic area or population group at a constant, baseline, prevalence or incidence rate that is higher in comparison to other areas or population groups [70].

Infection control programs are continually faced with competing priorities and reduced or insufficient resources. Expectations of expanded surveillance and reporting, whether from internal, regulatory, or public (Surveillance), demand time from practitioners, often at the expense of education, observation, and behavior modification (Prevention) [63].

Combating communicable diseases depends upon surveillance, preventive measures and where appropriate, outbreak investigation and the institution of control measures [43]. Burden of disease type analyses would also be useful to highlight the hazard areas contributing most infectious diseases and therefore particularly deserving of surveillance [111].

2.11.2 Communicable Diseases and Immunization in Iraq

There are a number of infectious diseases, both zoonotic and non-zoonotic, in many developing countries where the conditions are favourable for their maintenance and spread. These diseases are often entrenched in such countries and continue to present a threat to neighbouring countries and regions, with potentially serious socioeconomic impacts [1]. Iraq is at risk of epidemics spreading from neighbouring countries because it lies on the routes of pilgrimage to Mecca and contains a number of holy shrines [112]. The control of communicable diseases represents a major challenge to those providing health care services in Iraq and neighboring countries. Communicable diseases are a major cause of mortality and morbidity in Iraq. Three of the major killers are acute lower respiratory infections (ALRI), diarrheal diseases and measles. ALRI and diarrhea alone account for 70% of deaths in children under 5 years of age. Outbreaks of diarrheal diseases are common in Iraq, with high incidence especially in the summer months. Many electricity-generating plants, water purification and sewage treatment plants were destroyed during the 1991 Gulf War, with a delay in or incomplete repair of these facilities. Visceral leishmaniasis has increased in central Iraq and the greater Baghdad area as a result of increased density of sand-fly vectors, movement of people and deterioration in the health status of the population [113]. The situation of communicable diseases in Baghdad as revealed in Annual report 2010 Iraqi ministry of health, can be seen in table number (2.2) below [114],

Communicable diseases distributed according to disease and incidence rate per (10,000) of population.

Table 2.2: Communicable Diseases Situation in Baghdad 2010 [114]

Communicable Disease	Directorate of Health (DOH)			
	Baghdad (Karkh) Population (3549800)		Baghdad (Russafa) Population (4097682)	
	Case	Rate	Case	Rate
AFP	92	0.26	67	0.16
Diphtheria	0	0.00	0	0.00
Pertussis	163	0.46	164	0.40
Measles	142	0.40	133	0.32
Rubella	10	0.03	10	0.02
Mumps	259	0.73	301	0.73
Neonatal Tetanus	2	0.01	1	0.002
Cholera	0	0.00	0	0.00
Cutaneous leishmania	332	0.94	21	0.05
Kala-Azar	87	0.25	54	0.13
Hydatid cyst	2	0.01	41	0.10
Malate fever	240	0.68	109	0.27
Rabies	4	0.01	5	0.01
Hepatitis	1458	4.11	1911	4.66
Meningitis	241	0.68	247	0.60
Schistosomiasis	0	0.00	0	0.00
Bacillus dysentery	3	0.01	0	0.00
Chicken pox	4607	12.98	4924	12.02
Typhoid	3346	9.43	4184	10.21

Immunization is a proven tool for controlling and eliminating life-threatening infectious diseases [115]. Vaccines prevent up to three million deaths each year and (750,000) children are saved from disability globally [116]. Immunizations are among the most successful and cost effective disease prevention interventions available [117]. Achievement of the regional expected results for monitoring and evaluation of Expanded Program for Immunization (EPI) is on track. Eighteen Countries are currently regularly monitoring district level coverage data. To further

strengthen monitoring and evaluation of EPI at district level, capacity building in data quality assessment was conducted for six priority countries (Afghanistan, Iraq, Pakistan, Somalia, Sudan and Yemen) in addition to Jordan [31]. Afghanistan and Iraq experienced measles outbreaks in 2009. Rapid implementation of measles vaccination campaigns was instrumental in containing these outbreaks [118] and below the immunization schedule in Iraq*[139].

Table 2.3: Immunization Schedule for Iraq 2011

Vaccine	Schedule
-BCG, oral polio vaccine zero dose (hepatitis B vaccine 1 in the first24 hour)	At Birth
- (DPT, Hib + hepatitis B vaccine) -Rota virus vaccine 1+ oral polio (OPV) vaccine 1	2 months
-(DPT + Hib) -Rota virus vaccine 2+ oral polio vaccine 2	4 months
- (DPT, Hib + hepatitis B vaccine) -Rota virus vaccine 3+ oral polio vaccine 3	6 months
-MCV (measles-containing vaccine) - Vit A 100,000 IU	9 months
MMR (measles-mumps-rubella vaccine)	15 months
-(DPT + Hib) - oral polio vaccine - Vit A 200,000 IU	18 months
-(DPT) - oral polio vaccine - MMR	4-6 years
TT (tetanus toxoid)	Child Bearing Age Women (CBAW) – 5 doses

(Source: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Health, Public health directorate, Immunization Department. Immunization Schedule for Iraq, 2011)

2.12 Health Situation in Iraq

Iraq itself had gone through a series of developments, which have immense implications on the health of the people of Iraq. Iraq has been witnessing years of turmoil, sanctions, wars and displacement, which directly (and indirectly) have affected the health system to the detriment of the people of Iraq [120].

During the evolution of healthcare in Iraq during the periods from 1921 to 1945 the health authorities was not able to overcome the problems of endemic diseases, which was associated with significant mortality. The lack of experts and specialized health cadres, poor health budget and the absence of a central health policy to eradicate endemic diseases were the main contributing factors to that failure. Failure of preventive health care during that period made the health authorities concentrating on curative medical care. However, during the period from 1948 to 1958 the establishment of the Institute of Endemic Diseases contributed to improvement in preventive care. [121].

2.12.1 Current Situation in Iraq

Iraq is witnessing a demographic and epidemiological transition, creating additional constraints for the health system in managing the double burden of communicable and non-communicable diseases and adapting the supply of services and human resources to emerging needs and higher population expectations. With relatively limited financial resources and increasing cost of care, providing universal access to health services remains a major concern for the government of Iraq [122].

The factors contributing to the deteriorating health status include poor investment in health development, poorly maintained health infrastructure, inappropriate management of the health sector, very

low household purchasing power, poor sanitation and water supply, unsafe food storage, smoking, unhealthy dietary patterns, and lack of exercise [123]. While a strong health system can help individual health programmes to deliver efficiently and effectively. When the health system functions well it provides a platform for health care delivery. When it performs below the level necessary to ensure efficient and effective delivery of services, the health system becomes a hindrance to health programmes and encourages fragmentation and a vertical approach [119].

2.12.2 Health Administration and Population

Iraq has embarked upon improving and modernizing its healthcare delivery system. Although, the MOH is as the main health care provider in Iraq. After six years of civil war, preceded by a decade of international economic sanctions, Iraqi health officials say health-care conditions across the country are improving, but are still desperate [124].

In 2004, the Iraqi MOH articulated its vision for primary health care as: “an accessible affordable available safe and comprehensive quality health service of the highest possible standard that is financially sound and founded on scientific principles in order to meet the present and future health needs of Iraqi people regardless of their ethnicity, geographic origin, gender or religious affiliation.” [121]. The government understands that public health strategies cannot be successful if they are not implemented at all levels of society, including homes, offices, schools, factories and public institutions [125]. The Ministry of Health's budget is currently mainly provided by government through Ministry of Finance and accounts for (4.9%) of the government budget. Such a level of

government spending is less than the average of high-middle income countries of the Eastern Mediterranean Region [123].

Main administrative structure of Iraq is the governorate. There are 18 governorates, three of which are in the Kurdistan region, Iraq's northern-most provinces. Each governorate is divided into districts (Qadha) and sub-districts (Nahia). Within sub-districts are both urban divisions or neighbourhoods (Mahalah) and rural divisions comprised of several villages (Muqataa). In total there are 120 districts and a further 394 sub-districts [126]. The population of Iraq is (32,326,011) distributed in 18 governorates (Approximately 70.9% of the population live in urban areas). Each one of the 18 governorates has a Directorate of Health (DOH), except for Baghdad, which has three Health Directorates [127]. Baghdad population is (7,647,482) male, (3,856,073) female, (3,791,409) children under five (1,300,072) female at child bearing age from 15-49 years is (1,682,446), There is 16 health sector & 165 Primary health care main centers in Baghdad [114]. The data flow chart for surveillance system in Iraq as it is in the Communicable Diseases Control Center (CDCC) can be shown in this diagram [128]

Figure 2.4: The Flow of Data for Surveillance in CDCC\Iraq [128]

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Study Design

This study was a descriptive, cross-sectional study conducted at 50 randomly selected (multistage sample) Primary Health Centers in Baghdad Governorate and both directorates of health (Karkh and Russafa) and communicable diseases control center (CDCC) of Iraq, data collection was by direct interview (face to face) and observation of equipment, materials and records.

3.2 Time of the Study

The data collection started from the 1st of November 2011 till the 1st of February 2012. The time sequence of data collection was continued for a period of 90 days, five days a week, and 6 hours a day (8 Am -2 Pm).

3.3 Place of the Study

The scene of the study was in surveillance units in health centers of Baghdad Governorate (the capital of Iraq), It is in the middle of the Iraq, Baghdad population is 7,647,482 persons. There are (16) health sectors and (165) Primary health care center in two Health Directorates distributed on the geographic map of Baghdad Governorate.

3.4 Sampling Design

Total number of primary health care centers in Baghdad Governorate had been taken from the official records in both directorate of Health in Baghdad, which were 165 at study time. The sample included primary health care centers with surveillance units, the total surveillance and communicable diseases units' involved in this study was 165. The sampling technique used in this study was multi-stage sample. By multistage sample, 50 units distributed from 50-health centers (Figure 3.1) had been

selected randomly from health sectors in both health directorates Karkh and Russafa as;

- Al-Karkh DOH: (5) sectors, (24) PHCC
- Al-Russafa DOH: (4) sectors, (26) PHCC

In addition to, Al-Karkh, Al-Russafa DOH and CDCC had been taken as complete sample for its level. All details about numbers and names of health sectors and centers illustrated in (**Appendix A**).

3.5 Approvals and permissions

Arrangements were done to get approvals from the Directorates of Health in Baghdad Governorate for all the included health centers in the study (**Appendix B**).

3.6 Data Collection

The data collection was made by the use of WHO generic questionnaires for assessment of National communicable disease surveillance and response system at three levels [9] with no modifications to it at all (**Appendix C**). The researcher at each level completed it. Eighty percent performance at all CDSS levels as the standard benchmark for each indicator had been taken in account, based on the study in Sudan [134] as an Arab country, where there was no such performance indicator for Iraq or other Arab countries in the Eastern Mediterranean Region. Also WHO and CDC Guide for the use of core Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response Indicators in the African Region [137].

The questionnaires were as:

- Central level (which was represented by CDC in Iraq).
- District level (which was represented by DOH in Baghdad).
- Health facilities level (which was represented by PHCCs).

The questionnaires filling includes both interview and observation items. The direct interview technique (face to face) was used with the managers of surveillance unit and the staff to fill the questionnaire. Revision and observation monitored by the investigator as a complementary measure for the assessment process, used to check records, registries, resources and all other materials and requirements that need observation by the researcher for questionnaires in the surveillance units.

3.7 Limitations of the Study

Every study had its limitations, the main limitations found for this study were:

1. The absence of surveillance unit manager or staff for many reasons as sickness, vacation or on health mission.
2. The nature of working system in health institutions (50% of health workers act on Saturday and Thursday). These limitations made the researcher obliged to return more than one time to the health facility to complete data collection with the respondents.
3. The study cannot be generalized to other governorates in Iraq, but due to similarities in the systems, other governorates might benefit from certain points in the discussion of results.
4. The limitations in the review study are related to different objectives and methodology in the studies making comparisons difficult.

3.8 Data Analysis

Data entry was done using computer Pentium IV directly to the statistical analysis program and statistical analysis was done by using the SPSS (statistical package of the social science) package version (18). For the surveillance questionnaire, the performance indicators were calculated using WHO questionnaire.

Data were summarized and frequency distribution tables were constructed. Tables were stratified according to the surveillance levels, and the findings were arranged through descriptive statistical measurements (frequency and percentage). The average percent of achievement of each core and support function was calculated by dividing the summation of achieved number of this function over the sub-systems on 50, which is the total number of assessed facilities for each level.

(Source: Al-Karkh DOH, Engineering Department, 2011)

Figure 3.1: distribution of the selected PHCC

* The unknown and not applicable answers was not mentioned in results because it was scored zero, and the results include the positive answers.

The National Manual of Surveillance (NSM) was present in 3 (6%) and not presents in 47 (94%) of the selected health facilities (Primary Health Care Centers), (figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: The Presence of National Surveillance Manual in Surveillance Units (n=50).

For case detection and registration of communicable diseases surveillance, table 4.1 demonstrates that registries are present in 49 (98%) of health facilities. There is difference among the health centers in correct filling of these registries, as the correct filling of registers was in 43 (86%) of health centers. Case definition for communicable diseases was present in 8 (16%) of health centers. The rate for use of standard case definition for diagnosing the communicable diseases was 8 (16%) and not used in 42 (84%) of health centers. Correct diagnosis of diseases was achieved in only 8 (16%) of health centers using the standard case definition.

Table 4.1: Case detection and registration in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Case Detection and Registration	Surveillance Units (n=50)	
	Freq.	%
The Presence of a clinical register	49	98%
The correct filling of the clinical register during the previous 30 days	43	86%
Presence of case definition of communicable diseases	8	16%
The Use of standard case definition for diagnosing the communicable diseases	8	16%
The Respondent correctly diagnose one of the country's priority diseases using a standard case definition	8	16%

Table 4.2; shows that the ability to collect specimens was mainly for blood and stool 50(100%), and no facilities to collect CSF in all PHCC. The availability of materials required to collect specimens was mainly for blood 50 (100%) and stool 49 (98%). The ability to handle sputum, stool, blood/serum and CSF until shipment from these centers to the next level was present in 44 (88%) of centers. The functional cold chain was present in 48 (96%) of health facilities. The transport media for stool present in 40 (80%) of health facility. Ninety percent (45) of health facilities have packing materials for shipment of specimens to next level.

Table 4.2: Case confirmation in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Case Confirmation	Surveillance Units (n=50)	
	Freq.	%
The Ability to collect the sputum	6	12%
The Ability to collect the stool	50	100%
The Ability to collect the blood	50	100%
The Ability to collect the cerpro-spinal-fluid (CSF)	0	0%
The Presence of materials required to collect sputum	6	12%
The Presence of materials required to collect stool	49	98%
The Presence of materials required to collect blood	50	100%
The Presence of materials required to collect CSF	0	0%
The Capacity to handle sputum, stool, blood/serum and CSF until shipment at this facility	44	88%
The Presence of functional cold chain at health facility	48	96%
The Presence of transport media for stool at health facility	40	80%
The Presence of packing materials for shipment of specimens at health facility	45	90%

In data reporting , 23 (46%) of centers under study shows that there is shortage in surveillance forms used for reporting during the last six months, while the health centers under study shows that no register and reporting for (Elimination, Epidemic prone and Major public health importance targeted diseases) (table 4.3).

Table 4.3: Data reporting in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Data Reporting	Surveillance Units (n=50)	
	Freq.	%
The Shortage of surveillance forms during the last 6 months	23	46%
The Presence of correct register of targeted diseases as for Eradication	0	0%
The Presence of correct register of targeted diseases as for Elimination	0	0%
The Presence of correct register of targeted diseases as for Epidemic prone	0	0%
The Presence of correct register of targeted diseases as for Major public health importance	0	0%

According to the number of reports that the health centers should send to higher level which is (1 report weekly and 1 report monthly) , the mean score of weekly reports was (11.40) compared to expected number for the last 3 months (12) and (2.92) for monthly reports compared to expected number for the last 3 months (3). The mean score for the weekly reports submitted on time was (11.14) and the mean score for the monthly reports submitted on time was (2.90), as illustrated in (table 4.4).

Table 4.4: The score of monthly and weekly reports according to the numbers of report in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Number of Reports	Score Mean \pm SD (Range)
Number of reports in the last 3 months compared to expected number ,Weekly.	11.40 \pm 2.50 (0-12)
Number of reports in the last 3 months compared to expected number ,Monthly.	2.92 \pm 0.44 (0-3)
Number of weekly reports submitted on time.	11.14 \pm 2.75 (0-12)
Number of monthly reports submitted on time.	2.90 \pm 0.46 (0-3)

Table 4.5 shows that mail (hand posting) was the main and only tool of data reporting for the system in a rate of 50 (100%). Respondents suggested that reporting could be improved by use of Electronic(38) 76%, Telephone 6 (12%), none 3 (6%), Electronic and Telephone 2 (4%), Mail 1 (2%).

Table 4.5: Types of reporting and ways to strengthen reporting according to staff in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Reporting		Surveillance Units (n=50)	
		Freq.	%
Type of reporting	Mail	50	100%
	Fax	0	0%
	Telephone	0	0%
	Radio	0	0%
	Electronic	0	0%
	Other	0	0%
Ways to strengthening reporting	Electronic	38	76%
	Telephone	6	12%
	None	3	6%
	Electronic and Telephone	2	4%
	Mail	1	2%

Inquiry about the data analysis indicates that all health facilities described data by sex 50 (100%), place 50 (100%) but the description of data by time was 48 (96%). None of health facilities has threshold level for action i.e. when the level of any disease occurrence become above the usual one, an action should be taken. The presence of demographic data was 50 (100%) and rates derived from demographic data scored 40 (80%), as shown in table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Data analysis in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Data Analysis	Surveillance Units (n=50)	
	Freq.	%
The Presence of description of data by age and sex	50	100%
The Presence of description of data by place (locality, village, work site and other)	50	100%
The Presence of description of data by time	48	96%
The Presence of line graph of cases by time	3	6%
The Presence of an action threshold for country priority diseases	0	0%
The Presence of demographic data	50	100%
The Presence of rates derived from demographic data	40	80%

Indicators of Epidemic preparedness and response evaluation also shown in (Figure 4.2). The results showed that 43 (86%) of the health facilities had a written case management protocol for at least one epidemic prone disease while it was absent in 7 (14%) of health facilities.

Figure 4.2: Epidemic preparedness in Surveillance Units (n=50).

In (figure 4.3) that illustrate the epidemic response, revealed that 36 (72%) of health facilities implement prevention and control measure for one epidemic prone disease while not implemented in 14 (28%). Acceptable case fatality rate for most recent outbreak (10% for Meningococcal, 1% for Cholera) was achieved in 24 (48%) and not achieved in 26 (52%) of health centers.

Figure 4.3: Epidemic response in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Figure 4.4; portrays the feedback from higher level to health facilities, which is 15 (30%) and absent for 35 (70%) of health facilities. Sixty-two percent (31) of health facilities were conducting meeting with community members within the last six months before the present survey while no meeting conducted in 19 (38%).

Figure 4.4: Feedback in Surveillance Units (n=50).

According to the number of feedback bulletin or reports that the health centers had received in the last year before the study, the mean score of feedback bulletin and reports was (3.24). The rate of attending community meetings in the past six months preceding the study was 62%, among these, the score of attending was 4.08 only.

Table 4.7: The score of Feedback according to the numbers of feedback and meeting in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Number of Feedback	Score Mean±SD
Number of feedback bulletin or reports has the health facility received in the last year	3.24±7.44
Number of meetings with the community members in the past six months	4.08±2.41

The supervision of surveillance activities during supervisory visits from the higher levels were 44 (88%). Surveillance data of communicable diseases was reviewed in 21 (42%) of health facilities by the supervisors(table 4.8).

Table 4.8: Supervision in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Supervision	Surveillance Units (n=50)	
	Freq.	%
The Presence of supervision in last 6 months	44	88%
The Presence of appropriate review of surveillance practices in supervision	21	42%

The bar chart that is shown below, displays the results of the training function in surveillance system. Training of the staff in disease surveillance and data management had a total achievement of 15 (30%) while 35 (70%) was not available in health centers for workers and staff of surveillance units in the health facilities (Figure 4.5).

Figure 4.5: Training in Surveillance Units (n=50).

The availability of resources at surveyed health facilities was variable. Electricity, posters and generator were present in all of the examined health facilities. Stationery were available in 48 (96%); while 40 (80%) of health facilities had calculators, 3 (6%) had printer, 5 (10%) had computers in surveillance unit and 2 (4%) of these health facilities had their special vehicles. Fourteen percent (7) had telephone service, 20 (40%) computers that have modems (internet line). Presence of megaphone scored 35 (70%), flipcharts or image box 3 (6%), VCR and TV set 49 (98%). Assessment of the availability of other surveillance resources showed that (30%, 20%, 8%, 94% and 92%) of health facilities had screen, projector, spray pump,

disinfectants and protection materials respectively. Bicycles, motorcycles, statistical package, fax and radio call were not present in all of the examined health facilities too. These resources were used to support all surveillance systems of infectious diseases (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Resources in Surveillance Units (n=50).

The satisfaction with surveillance system in health centers revealed that only 10 (20%) were satisfied while 40 (80%) were not satisfied with the system for all those who works at surveillance units. Forty-eight (24) who agreed with the presence of opportunities for integration of surveillance activities and functions while 26 (52%) of centers found no opportunities there for integration (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.7: Satisfaction with surveillance system in Surveillance Units (n=50).

When staff asked how the disease surveillance implementation could be improved 66% of the respondents mentioned increase personnel, 64% facilities, 50% training, 20% communication, 18% proposed improving Transport, 14% technologies, 8% physicians in communicable diseases, 6% labs, 4% improve reporting and the same number for lectures, 2% changing the surveillance system and 2% surveillance centers as showed in (table 4.9).

Table 4.9: Ways of surveillance system improvement according to workers in Surveillance Units (n=50).

Ways of Surveillance System Improvement	Surveillance Units	
	Freq.	%
Increase personnel (staff)	33	66%
Facilities	32	64%
Training	25	50%
Communication	10	20%
Transport	9	18%
Technologies	7	14%
Physicians in communicable diseases	4	8%
Labs	3	6%
Improve reporting	2	4%
Lectures	2	4%
Changing the surveillance system	1	2%
Surveillance Centers	1	2%

Table 4.10: Summarizes the average percent of achievement of each core and supportive functions with presence of NSM for the surveillance system evaluation results at health centers level (n=50), district level (N=2) and central level (N=1). This assessment showed that all levels in data reporting scored high rates, 95% in PHCC, 98% in district level and 100% for the central level. The data analysis showed that 80% of data had been analyzed in health centers, 85% in district and in central level 100%. Epidemic preparedness in all levels came almost with same results of data analysis as (86%, 83% and 100%) respectively. PHCC scored 72% in Epidemic response while 100% for both district and central level. In feedback also, PHCC scored 66% while district and central level both scored 100%. Supervision for health centers was 65% and less in district which is 50%,

as with other results the central level scored 100% too. Thirty percent was the achievement in training for health centers, 96% for district level and central level 100%. Presence of resources was very low in health centers which scored 21%, district 66% and for central level was 77%. National Surveillance Manual was present in just 6% of presence in in health centers while scored 100% in both levels the district and the central.

Table 4.10: Total achievement of core and supportive functions at the health centers, districts and central level

Core and Supportive Functions		% of achievement		
		PHCC level (n=50)	District level (n=2)	Central level (n=1)
1	Data reporting	95%	98%	100%
2	Data analysis	80%	85%	100%
3	Epidemic preparedness	86%	83%	100%
4	Epidemic response	72%	100%	100%
5	Feedback	66%	100%	100%
6	Supervision	65%	50%	100%
7	Training	30%	96%	100%
8	Resources	21%	66%	77%
National Surveillance Manual		6%	100%	100%

5. Discussion

Surveillance provides information for action against infectious disease threats. Basic surveillance functions include detecting and reporting cases of disease, analyzing and confirming this information to identify outbreaks and clarify longer-term trends, and applying the information to inform public health decision making. When effective, surveillance can facilitate (1) timely action to control outbreaks, (2) informed allocation of resources to meet changing disease conditions, and (3) adjustment of disease control programs to make them more effective. According to CDC, factors that can be taken into account in evaluating surveillance systems include their ease of operation; the extent to which health care providers and laboratory personnel actually provide the system with information; and the system's ability to identify cases of disease, accurately diagnose them, and generate timely and accurate information on disease events and trends [2].

5.1 National Surveillance Manual:

In this study there were only 6% of health centers (surveillance units) had National Surveillance Manual. This very low percentage may be because there is no complete guideline as a book for surveillance in the directorates of health in Baghdad and CDCC, no follow up in PHCC for new instructions, where the new instructions and updates come as an annually plan from the central level vertically, while old plans just left on shelves and forgotten. Also may be due to there is no permanent staff or persons in charge, where the study found some surveillance units run by newly graduated doctors and they are in rotation stage or by physicians which they manage more than one program in the same time. These results were lower than the results obtained by Abbas study in Wasit, Iraq 2010, where it is showed that just 41.2% of health facilities have surveillance manual [57]. In Sudan a study by Sahal *et.al.* 2011, showed that 13.3% of

health facilities have surveillance manual [91]. In Mozambique 2006, a report by WHO for assessment of Epidemiological Disease Surveillance system found that only 34.8 % of the health facilities had national epidemiological disease surveillance guidelines [75]. This study disagrees with Ibrahim *et.al.* in Saudi Arabia 2009 where 57.6% of health facilities have surveillance manual [129]. The difference between both studies may be due to the increased knowledge level for the staff and management manner in their surveillance units.

5.2 Case detection and registration:

This study revealed that the availability of clinical registers in all health facilities was 98%. This very high rate may be attributed to the registration that checking more than one time and by many persons in PHCC also physicians in medical units enforce patients to register in communicable diseases unit if they had one. These results were similar to the results from Al-Jawadi *et.al.* study in Mosul, Iraq 2008 where clinical registers scored 100% [130]. Results from Wasit, Iraq 2010 by Abbas, clinical registers also high as 94.1% [57]. This study came with higher percentage in clinical registers than Ibrahim *et.al.* [129] where scored 75.8%.

The correct filling of the clinical register in this study was 86% of registration which is higher than Al-Jwadi *et.al.* study in Mosul, Iraq 2008 where the results of the study was 81.8% [130] also higher than Ibrahim *et.al.* study where just 60.6% of registers filled correctly [129], but in Wasit the results was very low where just 22.9% of centers correctly filled the registers [57].

For the presence of case definition of communicable diseases in this study, it was declared that the PHCC which had case definition for communicable diseases under surveillance was just 16%. This low

percentage may be attributed to same reasons which lead to the decrease in percentage of national surveillance manual availability, an addition to, there was an old book published by Iraqi Ministry of Health\CDCC 1999 [138] and was distributed to all health facilities and it was found in some centers where the workers in the surveillance units still have it and not found in many centers also many workers lack of knowledge about the case definition. These results agree with Abbas, Wasit, Iraq 2010 [57] where just 5.9% of health facilities had case definition of communicable diseases. Also agree with study in Uganda 2000, where 35% of health facilities the presence of case definition was found [131]. Ibrahim *et.al.* in Saudi Arabia 2009 found that 54.5% of health facilities had case definition for communicable diseases [129]. The difference between the two studies may be because the case definition was included with National Surveillance Manual in health facilities. Krause *et.al.* in Berlin, Germany 2005 [49] expressed that the existence of case definitions was unknown to 86.5% of the respondents; 75.2% expressed the desire to have case definitions available.

The study also revealed that the use of standard case definition for diagnosing the communicable diseases was in 16% of the health centers and this low percentage may be reasonable because of the presence of standard case definition was just 16%. These results were not consenting with Ibrahim *et.al.* [129], they revealed that 57.5% were using standard case definition and this difference may be attributed to the same reason that case definition was included with National Surveillance Manual in health facilities.

5.3 Case confirmation:

The result of this study shows that the ability to collect sputum, stool, blood and CSF was (12%, 100%, 100% and 0%) respectively, in the health centers. This low percentage of ability to collect sputum may be due to

these not all centers have units to T.B examination and the zero percent of CSF sample collection may be because the centers laboratories were not able to deal with CSF samples and physician prefer sending suspected cases to hospitals for more confirmation and they consider it a surgical procedure. Results from Saudi Arabia study in 2009 [129] revealed that ability to collect sputum, stool, blood and CSF was (75.8%, 69.7%, 75.8% and 24.2%) respectively.

The presence of materials required for collecting sputum, stool, blood and CSF was (12%, 98%, 100% and 0%) respectively, which was almost the same of ability to collect the samples. Ibrahim *et.al.* [129] found (60.6%, 51.5%, 48.5% and 24.2%) respectively. These differences between both studies may be because of the ability of the their laboratories in the health centers.

Also this study is clearing up that 88% of sample had the capacity to handle sputum, stool, and blood until shipment at health facilities. The presence of functional cold chain at health facility was 96%. The presence of transport media for stool at health facility was 80%. The presence of packing materials for shipment of specimens at health facility was 90%. These high percentages may be due to availability of electricity and materials required to keep and store the samples in these health facilities, the continuous follow up and support of MOH to health centers and its laboratories. This study was higher than Ibrahim *et.al.* study [129] where it is scored just 45.5% was the capacity to handle the samples, 60.6% the presence of functional cold chain, 42.4% the presence of transport media for stool and 48.5% the presence of packing materials for shipment of specimens. Study result also higher than study results in Georgia (a former republic of the Soviet Union) in 2002 [132]. Lower percentage may be because suspected cases that need laboratory investigations were referred to more advanced laboratories in health facilities.

5.4 Data reporting:

The study found that, the shortage of surveillance forms (lack of reporting forms) during the last 6 months was 46%. These forms distributed by CDCC through chain of command to finally be at surveillance units in the health facilities to be filled and send back weekly or monthly according to timelines and reporting priority of diseases and instructions of MOH. A study in Mosul, Iraq [130] reported no shortage in the forms required for reporting. Abass in Wasit, Iraq 2010 found shortage in 51% of centers [57]. Results from Uganda [131] showed that 65% of facilities lacked an adequate supply of reporting forms during the 6 months preceding the study. This evection perhaps due to, differences in the resources available for health care between the countries.

In the present study the results showed that, the mean score of weekly and monthly reports scored 11.40 (95%) reports from 12 in three months which should be send weekly and 2.92 (97.3%) reports from 3 in three months which should be send monthly. The timelines for these reports to be submitted on time to the next level was, weekly 11.14 (92.8%), monthly 2.90 (96.6%) of reports. These high rates may reflect the nature of system in Iraq which obligates health centers to send reports even if there were no cases of communicable disease. These results resemble to the evaluation of Iraqi MOH 2008 for the health system in presence of good reporting and notification process [46]. Positive results had been revealed by Abbas in Iraq [57] where 74.5% weekly reports completed and 84.3% submitted on time. Nsubuga *et.al.* in Study in Tanzania found just 35% of reports was submitted on time [41].

Type of reporting in this study revealed that 100% of PHCC using regular mail (hand posting) as the main way for sending the weekly and monthly reports, receiving documents from other facilities and all forms of formal writing, also no using of fax, radio call and E-mail. This very high

result may be because the formal writing in the MOH and all the systems in Iraq still use the ordinary mail. Agreement with Al Jawadi *et.al.* results from Iraq that shows hand posting was the main tool of data reporting and none of these health facilities have other communication technologies as E-mail, fax or radio call [130]. While in Australia 2004, as an example of developed country, data are received from various clinical sources via papers, telephone and fax [133].

5.5 Data analysis:

The data analysis demonstrates that description of data by place, sex and time was (100%, 100% and 96%) respectively. The presence of line graph of cases by time in this study was 6%. The presence of an action threshold for country priority diseases in this study was absent. The presence of demographic data in the health facilities that used in surveillance system was 100%. The description of data was high may be due to good recording of information for visitors to health facilities and the nature of health system and how the health centers were located according geographical area. The low percentage of presence of line graph of cases may be devoted to lack of computers and trained staff to do line graph, where it is almost found in higher level. No signs had been noticed about availability of action threshold for priority diseases in the country. 100% was the rate of presence of demographic data in PHCC, where through observation, it is found that epidemiological map and rates of population in each health center which were provided by higher level. The study in Mosul agreed with this study where (80%, 100% and 60%) respectively, was the description of data by place, sex and time. 0.6% was the presence of line graph which is very close to the present study. Only 12.1% of centers had an action threshold. Also 100% was found by this study for presence of demographic data [130]. Abbas 2010, proclaimed presence of place

description 70.6%, time description 90.2% and only 3.9% perform cases line graph [57]. Lower percentage presented by Ibrahim *et al* 2009, where 33.3% description by place, 39.3% description by time. 12.1% of centers conducting line graph for cases. Action threshold was 20.2% for a country-priority disease. Also Ibrahim *et.al.* study explains presence of demographic data in 15.2% of health centers [129]. Study in Khartoum, Sudan 2010 by Sahal *et.al.* described data analysis as, Performing trend analysis 0.0%, Aggregate case data by demographic category 100% [134].

5.6 Epidemic preparedness:

At the health facilities level the presence of national plan of epidemic preparedness, written case management protocol and a rapid response team with action threshold of action can enhance their ability to respond to an epidemic prone disease after notification of an outbreak. Also 86% of health facilities had written case management protocol and that was obvious during the study where case management protocol provided by primary health districts through DOH to PHCC. The study disagreed with Abass 2010 in Iraq, low percentage obtained in that study which was 11.8% [57]. Better results from Ibrahim *et.al.* in Jeddah 2009 about presence of written case management protocol which was 57.6% [129].

5.7 Epidemic response:

Regarding epidemic response, 72% of health facilities implemented prevention and control measures for one epidemic prone disease, based on a local data the staff in health centers did many control and prevention procedures for suspected and confirmed cases diagnosed in the same centers, or centers get informed from higher level if diagnosis made in hospital or other health facility. Acceptable case fatality rate for most recent outbreaks was achieved in 48% of PHCC, and this low percent may

be not because other PHCC not achieved acceptable case fatality rate but because they don't know the outcome of cases after their referral to hospitals with no feedback from those hospitals. In comparison with Abbas study this study results was higher, where Abbas study explain that just 21.6% of health centers implemented prevention and control measures [57]. In agreement with Ibrahim *et.al.* study where scored 60.6% [129]. Also close results from Nsubuga *et.al.* in United Republic of Tanzania 2002 [41].

5.8 Feedback:

The results showed that feedback from higher level to health facilities was 30% and that percentage below the standards. One of the great problems discovered in this study was the poor feedback from higher levels to surveillance units and that may affect on the performance of staff which they consider it kind of neglecting and cutting channels of connection with higher levels according to them. This may be belong to weakness in coordination between primary health sectors and hospitals about cases sent for more confirmation, also published bulletins from MOH about communicable diseases were very little. Sixty two percent of health facilities were conducting meeting with community leaders within the last six months preceding the present survey with mean of 4.08 ± 2.41 from six meeting should achieved as one meeting monthly, these meetings with community members (local council) are very useful to discuss the last health problems in the area and for co-support with other facilities. In Iraq, the study of Abbas 2010 found feedback or report on surveillance from higher level in only 15.7% and that agreed with this study [57]. Al-Jwadi *et.al.* from Iraq agreed with this study too in presence of poor feedback where Al-Jwadi found just 3% of health facilities received feedback from higher level, while disagree about conducting the meeting with community

member where the study declared that just 1.2% of centers were attended and that may be because of the security situation in Mosul [130]. Ibrahim *et.al.* was close in study result (24.2%) to this study in presence of feedback from higher level [129]. Also Nsubuga *et al* 2002 from Tanzania represent the same percentage 36% [41]. In Republic of Armenia, study by Wuhib *et.al.* 2002 found feedback should provide to all reporting sources and share information across vertical program lines and with officials throughout the public health community in a timely fashion. A bulletin could include descriptions of important outbreak investigations, disease-specific analyses of surveillance data, graphic and tabular information on selected diseases, indicators of community health, and recommendations for public health concerns [135].

5.9 Supervision:

The presence of supervision in last 6 months for surveillance units in PHCC from higher level was 88% in this study. These supervisory visits made by primary health districts at most, DOH and sometimes from MOH. In this process of supervision, there must be documentation during the visits, so the presence of appropriate review of surveillance practices in supervision in the study scored 42%. This discrepancy between the percentage of presence of supervision (88%) and presence of appropriate review (42%) may be due to that the supervisor may don't have information about surveillance or the supervision was to health center in general. 42% may represent just the supervisors whom came from surveillance units in higher level, also this may reveals the lack of one of the primary objective of the communicable diseases surveillance. In developed countries, the supervision functions are done regularly through competent and qualified staff, with much more resources, and clear assignment of responsibility and accountability among authorized

surveillance personnel [136]. Al-Jwadi *et.al.* in Mosul got close results to this study, where 67.5% Surveillance activities supervised in the last 6 months, 5.5% of surveillance data reviewed during the visit [130].

5.10 Training:

This study demonstrated the availability of training in diseases surveillance and epidemic management which was 30%. This low percentage may be because of two reasons: (1) there is no permanent staff or persons in charge in surveillance units, and that is the same reason which leads to decrease in percentage of National Surveillance Manual presence, which explained before (2) the absence of pure Surveillance training about surveillance practices. Abbas in Wasit 2010, showed that more than half (52.7%) of health workers in charge of surveillance reported received training [57]. The study of Al-Jwadi *et.al.* in Mosul 2008 demonstrated that training in disease surveillance was 69.8% and Training in epidemic management was 28.5% [130]. Ibrahim *et.al.* also disagreed with this study where scored 66.7% [129]. In Uganda, 62% of the staff received training on use of surveillance forms [131]. This study result may be lower than these studies because the lack of centralized training, public health (surveillance) expertise, plus reasons mentioned above and that need to increase and improve the training to be enough to staff.

5.11 Resources:

The availability of resources at health facilities surveyed was variable. Resources in surveillance units putting up these results, which showed a complete presence for some and deficiency or absence for others. The most important results gained from this study were almost complete presence of electricity, stationery, disinfectants and protection materials. Also the lack or complete absence of the most important resources which should be available in the surveillance units as vehicles 4%, computers 10%,

statistical package (*SPSS*, *Epi Info* or others) 0.0%, fax and radio call 0.0% too and spray pump 8%. The diminishing in basic resources may hamper the work of staff and performance of the whole surveillance system. Results from Iraq by Abbas [57] revealed this; stationery 82.4%, Computers 9.8% and 7.8% had statistical package (*SPSS*). Vehicles only 3.9% and that agree with the present study. Another study from Iraq by Al-Jwadi *et.al.* [130] calculators were present in all of the examined health facilities, Electricity Generators were available in 94.1%; while 85.3% of health facilities had telephone, 88.3% had stationary, more than three-quarters (76.5%) had computers and 29.4% of these health facilities had their special vehicles. Almost one tenth (8.8%) had spray pump and disinfectants and none of them have radio call for urgent notification. Ibrahim *et al* [129] found that 63.6% of health facilities had Stationery, 54.5% had Computers 6.1% had statistical package and 48.5% had vehicles. The study of Sahal *et al* in Sudan 2010 got these results, presence of functioning telephone 80%, computers 14.7%, spray pump 0.0%, disinfection materials 65.3% and protection materials 60.7% [91]. In Uganda 2000, stationery 75%, calculators 77%, telephone 27% and radio call 14% [131]. Nsubuga *et.al.* from Tanzania found that telephone 44 % and radio call 6% vehicle 34% computers 16% [41]. Almost all studies agreed that there was deficiency in resources especially in presence of computers, statistical programs, radio call and spray pump that need improvements. These results indicate variable use of resources and finances in different countries. Nevertheless the availability of generators, calculators, stationary and statisticians can help the core activities to simplify the registration and reporting procedures.

5.12 Satisfaction with surveillance system:

The satisfaction with surveillance system in health centers according to staff and persons in charge in the surveillance units in the health

facilities revealed that only 20% were satisfied while 80% were not satisfied with the system and its activities. The opinions about surveillance system reflects the fact of that cadres may lack information about surveillance and how its work or they already recognized the defects and they have the ways for improvements and developments. The opportunities for integration of surveillance activities and functions to be complete program and merge all other units which are concern with communicable diseases, mentioned by 48% of respondents. This study agrees with Tanzanian study where it is found that 38% of respondents not satisfied [41]. Disagreement with Mozambique study2006 [75] 81% of the respondents were satisfied with the performance of epidemiological surveillance. This difference between both studies may be due to old creation of epidemiological surveillance system in Mozambique since 1979 according to the study.

This improvements ways that suggested by staff in the surveillance units, higher percentage was 33 (66%) for increase personnel (staff), 32 (64%) for facilities and 25 (50%) for training. In Mozambique 30 (40.5%) of the respondents mentioned training, four (5.4%) mentioned supervision and the same number proposed increasing the staff and providing manuals [75].

5.13 Total achievement

The total achievements of evaluated domains had been calculated according to all questions or to specific questions which represent those domains [130].For CDCC, we chose it as the central level for Baghdad where both DOH collect information and send it to CDCC, so the complete and final result found there. All domains at this level scored 100% except resources scored 77%, and that may be accepted results for level represents whole country. Also on districts level, all domains showed results higher than standard benchmark which is 80% except supervision 50% and

resources 66%. For those domains below the standard benchmark and those with slightly higher than benchmark, the proper improvements will be necessary to make system close to perfection. On the other hand the achievements of primary health care centers (health facilities level) for surveillance system assessment came with lower results than other levels, just data reporting, data analysis and epidemic preparedness was above the benchmark. Epidemic response, feedback and supervision was close to standard benchmark and need more attention to increase the percentage of achievement but at all still under acceptable limit. Results of resources showed very low percentage of achievement, where just 21% of PHCC, had enough resources, also training was low too where scored 30%. These deficiencies in core and supportive functions may be because of the gap between health system in Iraq and the development in health sector in the world that happened during last three decades where Iraq was in war and sanction.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusions

This assessment has revealed strengths and weaknesses in the communicable disease surveillance system in Baghdad Governorate, and the study has reached the following conclusions:

1. The national surveillance manual for communicable diseases was not present in complete form in surveillance units at health facilities.
2. Absence of newly and updated case definition for communicable diseases.
3. Staffs in surveillance units at health facilities don't know the targeted diseases for eradication, elimination, epidemic prone and Major public health importance in the country.
4. Complete absence of knowledge about action threshold for country priority diseases.
5. Obvious reduction in feedback as bulletins and reports for the health facility level.
6. Weakness in the presence of appropriate review of surveillance practices in supervision on surveillance units from the supervisors.
7. Training of staff about surveillance and epidemics management was very poor.
8. There is clear deficiency in different resources for surveillance system especially the computers, fax, statistical package, internet services and transportation at all levels.
9. Poor satisfaction with the surveillance system.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the Communicable Diseases Surveillance System (CDSS) in Baghdad Province needs to:

1. Strengthen the quality, core activities and supportive functions of the surveillance at all levels of the health system.
2. Formulation of clear written objectives for CDSS at all levels should be the first priority.
3. Forming an electronic network for reporting between districts and health facilities would be beneficial and make the raw surveillance data more accessible.
4. An urgent intervention is needed to build a system of updated, advanced data analysis both for the routine surveillance and for outbreaks to make use of the large amount of data collected by the system at different levels.
5. The system should build a strong collaborative link with the laboratories network.
6. The system should implement proper documentation methods for all the CDSS data collected mainly for the urgent notification of communicable diseases and outbreaks data as well as for zero reporting.
7. The surveillance system needs to develop a standard, regular and effective feedback system. The challenge is to respond quickly and properly to epidemics, thus formulation of standard rapid response team at all levels is the very first step in building effective epidemic preparedness in the province.
8. Adequate human resources (community health physicians, epidemiologist and statisticians) at lower levels of the surveillance system as well as creation of incentives system, which would maintain committed personnel in the CDSS, are needed.

9. Advanced training of all workers in surveillance units about surveillance activities, epidemics and data management.
10. Provision of supported, documented supervisory visits to the different levels and timely feedback might create additional support to sustain an effective CDSS that guides the public health decision making in Baghdad Province.

Summary

Surveillance of communicable diseases is a public health corner stone. Routine notification data on communicable diseases are used as a basis for public health action as well as for policy-making. Surveillance systems must detect new communicable diseases as well as recognize and track diseases that currently are, or have the potential to become, of major public health importance.

The general objective of this study is to assess the core activities and supportive functions of the communicable diseases surveillance system in term of structure, performance, epidemic preparedness and response at all health facilities level in Baghdad.

This study was a descriptive, cross-sectional study conducted at 50 Primary Health Care Centers which randomly selected (Multi-stage sample) in Baghdad and both directorates of health (Karkh and Russafa) and Communicable Diseases Control Center of Iraq, from the first of November 2011 till the first of February 2012.

The data collected by direct interview with the managers of Surveillance Units, observation of records and documents, materials and equipment by using World Health Organization generic questionnaires for assessment of National communicable disease surveillance.

The results showed that National Surveillance Manual was present in 6% of health centers. Data reporting was very good for achieving a rate of 95% of reporting. Data analysis scored 80% without conducting line graphs for communicable diseases. Epidemic preparedness was more than the recommended standard indicators (80%). Also 72% was the achievement of epidemic response in health centers. Feedback was less than standards which was just 66% of total achievement.

Supervision on surveillance system was present in 65% of health centers. The training was positive for 30% and resources 21%, all that for Primary Health Care Centers level. The next levels both, district and central level had achieved very good rate except in resources domain (66% and 77%) respectively.

In conclusion, Surveillance of communicable diseases in Baghdad is good in some parameters and deficit in others (which is Training, Resources and expertise).

This study recommends improving the surveillance system through increasing the training, provide more expertises, copying with developed countries experiences in this field and using the electronic technologies in reporting and data analysis.

- 1) Food And Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, World Organization for Animal Health, United Nations Children’s Fund, United Nations System Influenza Coordinator, World Health Organization, The World Bank. Contributing to One World, One Health; A Strategic Framework for Reducing Risks of Infectious Diseases at the Animal–Human–Ecosystems Interface, 14 October 2008.
- 2) United States General Accounting Office (GAO). Global Health; Challenges in Improving Infectious Disease Surveillance Systems. Global Health. August 2001.GAO-01-722.
- 3) Pan American Health Organization (PAHO). An integrated approach to communicable disease surveillance. Epidemiological Bulletin, 2000; 21(1):1–4.
- 4) Karimi A, Kadivar MR, Fararoe M , Alborzi A. Active case finding of communicable diseases in the south of the Islamic Republic of Iran. East Mediterranean Health J 2000;6(2/3):487- 93.
- 5) Stenhem M, Örtqvist Å, Ringberg H, Larsson L, Olsson-Liljequist B, Hæggman S et al. Validity of routine surveillance data: a case study on Swedish notifications of methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus. Euro Surveillance J 2009;14/30:412-417.
- 6) World Health Organization, Department of Communicable Disease ,Surveillance and Response. Technical Review on Monitoring And Evaluation Protocol for Communicable Disease Surveillance and Response Systems. Report of a WHO Meeting. Geneva, Switzerland 7–9 July 2004. World Health Organization. 2004. (WHO/CDS/CSR/LYO/2004.15).
- 7) Rebecca A. Meriwether. Blueprint for a National Public Health Surveillance System for the 21st Century: National Public Health

- Surveillance System. *Public Health Management Practice J.*(1996). 1996;2(4):16-23.
- 8) Salman ST. Iraqi guidelines for community health management: a problem solving approach. Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Health, Directorate of Medical Operations and Specialized Services 2010.
 - 9) World Health Organization, Department of Communicable Disease ,Surveillance and Response. Protocol for the Assessment of National Communicable Disease Surveillance and Response Systems: Guidelines for Assessment Teams. World Health Organization (2001). WHO/CDS/CSR/ISR/2001.2.
 - 10) Modeste Nn, Tamayose TS . Dictionary of public health promotion and education: terms and concepts. 2nd edition. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. San Francisco. 2004. p:123.
 - 11) Thacker SB, Stroup D. Public health surveillance. In Brownson RC, Petitti DB. *Applied epidemiology : theory to practice*. New York; Oxford University Press, Inc; 2000.p.105-135.
 - 12) Dorland's Illustrated Medical Dictionary 31st ed. Philadelphia: Saunders; 2007. Surveillance; p.1835.
 - 13) Tomar SL. Public Health Perspectives on Surveillance for Periodontal Diseases; Surveillance for Periodontal Diseases. *Periodontol J.* July 2007; Vol.78. No.7 (Suppl.):1380-1386.
 - 14) World Health Organization, Regional Office for the Western Pacific. A Practical Guide to Harmonizing Virological and Epidemiological Influenza Surveillance, November 2008.
 - 15) Jani J.V., Jani I.V., Araújo C., Sahay S., Barreto J., Bjune G. Assessment of routine surveillance data as a tool to investigate measles outbreaks in Mozambique. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 2006; 6:29.

- 16) World Health Organization, Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Surveillance of communicable diseases: a training manual. Alexandria, World Health Organization Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean, 1998.
- 17) World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe. Policy guidance on water-related disease surveillance. World Health Organization (2011).
- 18) World Health Organization, Department of Vaccines and Biologicals. Making surveillance work .Module 4: Data management. World Health Organization 2001. WHO/V&B/01.11.P.4.
- 19) Azar F.E.F., Masoori N., Meidani Z., Paul L. Proposal for a modernized Iranian notifiable infectious diseases surveillance system: comparison with USA and Australia. Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal (EMHJ) 2010; Vol. 16 No.7:771-777.
- 20) Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Health, Expanded program of immunization. Acute Flaccid Paralysis Field Manual for Communicable Diseases Surveillance Staff. 2009.
- 21) Runge-Ranzinger S, Horstick O, Marx M , Kroeger A. What does dengue disease surveillance contribute to predicting and detecting outbreaks and describing trends. Tropical Medicine and International Health. August 2008; Vol. 13 No. 8:1022–1041.
- 22) World Health Organization, Department of Vaccines and Biologicals. Making surveillance work . Module 3: Logistics management. World Health Organization 2001. WHO/V&B/01.10.
- 23) World Health Organization, Department of Vaccines and Biologicals. Making surveillance work . Module 1: Rapid assessment of surveillance for vaccine-preventable diseases. World Health Organization 2001. WHO/V&B/01.08.

- 24) U.S. Department Of Health And Human Services, Public Health Service Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Principles Of Epidemiology, 2nd Edition: An Introduction to Applied Epidemiology and Biostatistics. Self-Study Course 3030-G, 2005.
- 25) U.S. Department Of Health And Human Services, Public Health Service Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Principles of Epidemiology in Public Health Practice. 3rd Edition: An Introduction to Applied Epidemiology and Biostatistics. Self-Study Course SS1000, 2009.
- 26) World Health Organization, Department of Vaccines and Biologicals. WHO–recommended standards for surveillance of selected vaccine-preventable diseases. May 2003. WHO/V&B/03.01.
- 27) World Health Organization, Department of Communicable Disease Surveillance and Response. WHO Report on Global Surveillance of Epidemic-prone Infectious Diseases. World Health Organization, 2000. WHO/CDS/CSR/ISR/2000.1.
- 28) World Health Organization, Department of Communicable Disease Surveillance and Response. WHO Recommended Surveillance Standards. Second edition. World Health Organization 1999 . WHO/CDS/CSR/ISR/99.2.
- 29) Communicable Diseases Section, Public Health Division, Victorian Department of Human Services. Surveillance of Notifiable Infectious Diseases in Victoria 1999. December 2000.
- 30) Kansas Department of Health and Environment ,Office of Surveillance and Epidemiology. Surveillance Guidelines of Reportable Diseases in Kansas : A Tool for Local Health Departments and Regional Coordinators. April 2010.
- 31) World Health Organization, Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Annual Report of the Regional Director 1 January—31

- December 2008, The Work of WHO in the Eastern Mediterranean Region World Health Organization 2009.
- 32)** Ackman DM, Birkhead G, Flynn M . Assessment of Surveillance for Meningococcal Disease in New York State,1991. Assessment of Surveillance. American Journal of Epidemiology.1996; Vol. 144, No. 1: 78-82.
- 33)** Malaysia, Ministry of Health, Surveillance for Infectious Disease, Disease Control Division. Case Definitions for Infectious Diseases in Malaysia. 2nd Edition. Jan 2006. MOH/K/EPI/32.02(HB).
- 34)** John T. J., Rajappan K., Arjunan K.K. Communicable diseases monitored by disease surveillance in Kottayam district, Kerala state, India. Indian J Med Res 120. August 2004:86-93.
- 35)** Jajosky R.A., Groseclose S.L. Evaluation of reporting timeliness of public health surveillance systems for infectious diseases. BMC Public Health J. July 2004:1-9. doi:10.1186/1471-2458-4-29
- 36)** UNAIDS/ WHO, Working Group on Global HIV/AIDS/STI Surveillance. Guidelines for effective use of data from HIV surveillance systems. World Health Organization 2004. UNAIDS/04.01.
- 37)** Spitalny KC. Learning to design new systems: communicable disease surveillance. J Public Health Management Practice 1996;2(4):40-41.
- 38)** Touch S., Grundy J., Hills S., Rani M., Samnang C., Khalakdina A. et al. Lessons from the field; The rationale for integrated childhood meningoenzephalitis surveillance: a case study from Cambodia. Bull World Health Organ 2009;87:320–324.
- 39)** World Health Organization, Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Communicable diseases in the Eastern Mediterranean Region, Prevention and control 2005–2009. World Health Organization 2011.

- 40) World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe. Strengthening health-system emergency preparedness: Toolkit for assessing health-system capacity for crisis management, Part 1. User manual. World Health Organization 2012.
- 41) Nsubuga P, Eseko N, Wuhib T, Ndayimirije N, Chungong S, McNabb SN. Structure and performance of infectious disease surveillance and response, United Republic of Tanzania, 1998. Bull World Health Organ 2002; 80(3):196-203.
- 42) Amato-Gauci A. , Ammon A. The Surveillance of communicable diseases in the European Union- a long-term strategy (2008–2013). EUROSURVEILLANCE J.2008; Vol . 13 . No. 4–6:1-3.
- 43) World Health Organization, Epidemic and Pandemic Alert and Response. Setting priorities in communicable disease surveillance. World Health Organization 2006. WHO/CDS/EPR/LYO/2006.3.
- 44) World Health Organization and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention .Technical Guidelines for Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response in the African Region, Brazzaville, Republic of Congo and Atlanta, USA.2010 ;1-398.
- 45) WHO, CDC, USAID, SARA, UNFIP. The Implementation of Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response in the African and Eastern Mediterranean Regions :Synthesis Report. May 2003.P.1-26.
- 46) Ministry of Health, Iraq. A Basic Health Services Package for Iraq. World Health Organization. January 2009. P.1-97.
- 47) Heymann, D.L. Control of Communicable Diseases Manual (18th ed.).Washington, American Public Health Association. 2004.
- 48) World Health Organization, Department of Communicable Diseases Surveillance and Response. Guidelines for the Surveillance

- and Control of Anthrax in Humans and Animals. 3rd Edition. World Health Organization 1998. WHO/EMC/ZDI/98.6.
- 49) Krause G., Ropers G., Stark K. Notifiable Disease Surveillance and Practicing Physicians. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*. March 2005; Vol. 11, No. 3:442-445.
- 50) Schramm M.M., Vogt R.L., Mamolen M. The Surveillance of Communicable Disease in Vermont: Who Reports?; *Public Health Reports in brief*. *Public Health Reports* .January-February 1991; Vol. 106, No. 1:95-97.
- 51) Migliori G.B., Spanevello A., Ballardini L., Neri M., Gambarini C., Moro M. L., et al. Validation of the surveillance system for new cases of tuberculosis in a province of Northern Italy. *European Respiratory Journal*. 1995; 8: 1252–1258.
- 52) Desenclos JC, Bijkerk H, Huisman J. Variations in national infectious diseases surveillance in Europe. *Lancet* 1993; 341: 1003–1006.
- 53) Nelesone T., Durrheim D.N., Speare R., Kiedrzyński T., Melrose W.D. Short communication: Strengthening sub-national communicable disease surveillance in a remote Pacific Island country by adapting a successful African outbreak surveillance model. *Tropical Medicine and International Health J*. January 2006; Vol,11 No.1:17–21.
- 54) Arizona Department of Health Services, Office of Infectious Disease Services. *Infectious Disease Epidemiology Programs: 2007 Annual Report*. 2009.
- 55) World Health Organization, *Disease Control in Humanitarian Emergencies, Global Alert and Response*. Early warning surveillance and response in emergencies, Report of the second WHO technical

- workshop,10–11 May 2011. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland .2011.
- 56)** Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Case Definitions for Infectious Conditions Under Public Health Surveillance. MMWR May 02, 1997; 46(RR10):1-55.
- 57)** Abbas T.M. Assessment of Surveillance of Childhood Vaccine Preventable Diseases at Health Facilities in Wasit Governorate / Iraq a Thesis submitted to Foundation of Technical Education, Collage of Health and Medical Technology, Baghdad, Iraq 2010.
- 58)** World Health Organization. Information for action: Developing a computer-based information system for the surveillance of EPI and other diseases. World Health Organization, Geneva.1998. WHO/EPI/GEN/98.15.
- 59)** Ministry of Labor, Health and Social Affairs of Georgia & National Center for Disease Control. Surveillance and Control of Communicable Diseases: Guidelines for Public Health Services in Georgia. Third Edition. Bethesda, MD: The Partners for Health Reformplus Project, Abt Associates Inc, November 2005.
- 60)** Richards C, Emori TG, Peavy G, Gaynes R. promoting quality through measurement of performance and response: prevention success stories. Emerg Infect Dis. 2001;7:299-301.
- 61)** Lasker RD, Humphreys BL, Braithwaite WR. Making a Powerful Connection: The Health of the Public and the National Information Infrastructure. Washington, DC: Report of the U.S. Public Health Service Public Health Data Policy Coordinating Committee; 1995.
- 62)** World Health Organization, Epidemic And Pandemic Alert And Response. Communicable disease alert and response for mass gatherings: key considerations. World Health Organization June 2008.

- 63) Wright MO. Automated surveillance and infection control: Toward a better tomorrow. *Am J Infect Control* 2008; Vol. 36 No. 3 Supplement 1 S1-6.
- 64) McGrow KM, Roys R, Maloney RC, Xiao Y. Using wireless technologies to improve information flow for interhospital transfers of critical care patients. *Crit Care Nurse*. 2004;24:66-72 114.
- 65) United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). Behaviour Change Communication In Emergencies: A Toolkit. United Nations Children's Fund Regional Office for South Asia (UNICEF ROSA), 2006. P;41.
- 66) Castillo-Salgado C. Trends and directions of global public health surveillance. *Epidemiologic reviews*. Apr 2010;32(1):93–109.
- 67) World Health Organization, South-East Asia Region, Western Pacific Region. Asia Pacific Strategy for Emerging Diseases. World Health Organization 2005.
- 68) Bonita R, Beaglehole R, Kjellström T. Basic epidemiology 2nd edition. World Health Organization 2006.
- 69) Wallace B. Epidemiology and Public Health. In: Wallace B (ed). Public health and preventive medicine. 15th ed.2008. The McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc..1998; p: 5-26.
- 70) Vundle Z. Steps In An Outbreak Investigation . Communicable Diseases Surveillance Bulletin. National Institute For Communicable Diseases. November 2007; Vol. 5, No. 4:3-5.
- 71) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Public Health Preparedness Capabilities: National Standards for State and Local Planning. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, March 2011.

- 72) World Health Organization, Regional Office for South-East Asia. Regional Strategy for Integrated Disease Surveillance Report of an Intercountry Consultation Yangon, Myanmar, 21-24 August 2002. World Health Organization. 2003. SEA-CD-130.
- 73) World Health Organization, Epidemic and Pandemic Alert And Response. Communicable disease surveillance and response systems: Guide to monitoring and evaluating. World Health Organization 2006. WHO/CDS/EPR/LYO/2006.2.
- 74) Surveillance and Epidemiology Branch Centre for Health Protection. Communicable Disease Surveillance Case Definitions (Version 6.3). Surveillance and Epidemiology Branch Centre for Health Protection Department of Health Hong Kong Special Administrative Region People's Republic of China Revised on 18 January 2012.
- 75) World Health Organization, Ministry of Health in Mozambique. Assessment of Epidemiological Disease Surveillance system in Mozambique, 13- Nov -4 Dec 2006.
- 76) Connolly MA (ed). Communicable disease control in emergencies: A field manual. World Health Organization, 2005. WHO/CDS/2005.27.
- 77) Koo D, Wetterhall SF. History and current status of the national notifiable diseases surveillance system. J Public Health Manag Pract. 1996;2:4-10.
- 78) Kilbourne EM. Informatics in public health surveillance: current issues and future perspectives. In: Wetterhall SF, ed. Proceedings of the 1992 International Symposium on Public Health Surveillance. Morb Mortal Wkly Rep .1992;41 (Suppl):91-99.
- 79) World Health Organization. Outbreak surveillance and response in humanitarian emergencies; WHO guidelines for EWARN implementation. World Health Organization Geneva, 2012. WHO/HSE/GAR/DCE/2012.1.

- 80) Wisner B, Adams J. Environmental health in emergencies and disasters :A Practical Guide. World Health Organization 2002.
- 81) World Health Organization ,Global Task Force On Cholera Control. Cholera Outbreak: Assessing The Outbreak Response And Improving Preparedness. World Health Organization, 2004. WHO/CDS/CPE/ZFK/2004.4.
- 82) World Health Organization, Department of Immunization, Vaccines and Biologicals. 8. Making disease surveillance work: Training for mid-level managers (MLM). World Health Organization 2008. WHO/IVB/08.08.
- 83) University of Minnesota Center for Public Health Preparedness. Public Health Emergency Preparedness: Disease Surveillance Skill Development Guide. The University of Minnesota. 2007.
- 84) World Health Organization, Department of Communicable Disease Surveillance and Response. Global Outbreak Alert and Response. Report of a WHO meeting. Geneva, Switzerland 26-28 April 2000. WHO/CDS/CSR/2000.3.
- 85) World Health Organization, Regional Office for South-East Asia. Combating Emerging Infectious Diseases in the South-East Asia Region. World Health Organization .2005. SEA-CD-139.
- 86) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Third Joint Meeting of the Networks for Surveillance of Emerging Infectious Diseases. Atlanta, Georgia, USA, 26–28 February 2004.
- 87) Government of Southern Sudan, Ministry of Health (GOSS). Southern Sudan Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response Assessment Report 2007.
- 88) World Health Organization , WHO Office for National Epidemic Preparedness and Response, Lyon, France, Department of Epidemic

- and Pandemic Alert and Response. Activity Report 2006. World Health Organization 2007. WHO/CDS/EPR/LYO/2007.2.
- 89)** Nsubuga P, Nwanyanwu O, Nkengasong JN, Mukanga D, Trostle M. Strengthening public health surveillance and response using the health systems strengthening agenda in developing countries. *BMC public health*. Jan 2010;10 (Suppl. 1):S5.
- 90)** Nsubuga P, White ME., Thacker SB., Anderson MA. , Blount SB, Broome CV. et al . *Public Health Surveillance: A Tool for Targeting and Monitoring Interventions*. In: Jamison DT., Breman JG., Measham AR, Alleyne G, Claeson M, Evans DB. and et al. *Disease Control Priorities in Developing Countries* . 2nd Edition. PP: 997-1015. New York. A copublication of The World Bank and Oxford University Press.
- 91)** Sahal N, Reintjes R, Mahgoub AE, Aro AR. Staff views about the quality of the communicable diseases surveillance system in Khartoum state, Sudan, 2005–2007: a qualitative study. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*.2011; Vol.17 No.7:565-569.
- 92)** M'Ikanatha NM, Lynfield R, Van Beneden CA, de Valk H (ed). *Infectious disease surveillance*. Malden: Blackwell Publishing Ltd; 2007.
- 93)** Kimball AM, Moore M, French HM, Arima Y, Ungchusak K, Wibulpolprasert S, et al. Regional Infectious Disease Surveillance Networks and their Potential to Facilitate the Implementation of the International Health Regulations. *Med Clin N Am* 92 .2008; 1459–1471.
- 94)** Scribner S, Franco LM, Ram S. *Improving Surveillance Systems: Building Support for Implementation: A User's Guide*. Abt Associates Inc.

- 95) Baker G, Easter S, Wilson N. A surveillance sector review applied to infectious diseases at a country level, *BMC Public Health* .2010; 10:332.
- 96) Cliff AD, Haggett P, Smallman-Raynor M, Stroup DF, Williamson GD. The importance of long-term records in public health surveillance: the US weekly sanitary reports, 1888-1912, revisited. *Journal of Public Health Medicine*. 1997; Vol.19, No.1:76-84.
- 97) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Updated Guidelines for Evaluating Public Health Surveillance Systems: Recommendations from the Guidelines Working Group. *MMWR*, July 27, 2001; 50(RR13):1-35.
- 98) Centre for Epidemiology and Research, NSW Department for Health. Population Health Surveillance Strategy NSW 2011 to 2020. NSW Department of Health, 2011.
- 99) UNAIDS. National AIDS programmes: a guide to monitoring and evaluation. Geneva, UNAIDS, 2000.
- 100) Jena AB, Mohanty KC, Devadasan N. An outbreak of leptospirosis in Orissa, India: the importance of surveillance. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 2004;9: 1016–1021.
- 101) World Health Organization .Rapid Risk Assessment of Acute Public Health Events. World Health Organization Geneva, Switzerland 2010.WHO/HSE/GAR/ARO/2012.1.
- 102) Loeb M, Smieja M, Smaill F. Introduction to evidence-based infectious diseases. In: Loeb M, Smieja M, Smaill F (Editors). *Evidence-Based Infectious Diseases* 2nd ed. London BMJ ,Blackwell Publishing Ltd. 2009.p.1-7.
- 103) Stuckler D, King L, Robinson H, McKee M. WHO's budgetary allocations and burden of disease:a comparative analysis. *The Lancet*. November,1,2008; 372:1563–69.

- 104)** Prinja S, Gupta M, Singh A, Kumar R. Effectiveness of planning and management interventions for improving age-appropriate immunization in rural India. *Bull World Health Organ* 2010;88:97–103 | doi:10.2471/BLT.08.059543.
- 105)** United States Government Accountability Office (GAO). Emerging Infectious Diseases, Review of State and Federal Disease Surveillance Efforts. Report to the Chairman, Permanent Subcommittee on Investigations, Committee on Governmental Affairs, U.S. Senate. September 2004. GAO-04-877.
- 106)** Hawker J, Begg N, Blair I, Reintjes R, Weinberg J. Communicable Disease Control Handbook 2nd edition. Blackwell Publishing Ltd. 2005.
- 107)** Pan American Health Organization. Humanitarian assistance in disaster situations: A guide for effective aid. Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) Washington, D.C, 1999.
- 108)** World Health Organization, Health Action in Crises. WHO'S Humanitarian Action 2008-2009, Biennial Work Plan To Support Who's Capacity For Work In Emergencies And Crises, Medium-Term Strategic Plan 2008-2013, Programme Budget 2008-2009. World Health Organization Geneva, Switzerland 2008. WHO/HAC/DOC/2008.5/rev.1.
- 109)** World Health Organization ,South-East Asia Region,Western Pacific Region. Asia Pacific Strategy for emerging diseases : 2010. World Health Organization, 2011.
- 110)** Carr JE, Martin MR, Clements CJ, Ritchie PLJ. Behavioral Factors in Immunization. In Behavioral Science Learning Modules , World Health Organization Geneva; 2000:1-10.

- 111) Pruss A, Kay D, Fewtrell L, Bartram J. Estimating the burden of disease from water, sanitation, and hygiene at a global level. *Environ Health Perspect* 2002, 110:537-542.
- 112) Al-Abbassi A.M, Ahmed S, Al-Hadithi T. Cholera epidemic in Baghdad during :1999clinical and bacteriological profile of hospitalized cases. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, 2005;Vol. 11, No.1/2:6-13.
- 113) World Health Organization. Communicable Disease Toolkit: Iraq Crisis. World Health Organization, March 2003. WHO/CDS/2003.17.
- 114) 2010 جمهورية العراق, وزارة الصحة. التقرير السنوي لعام 2010.
- 115) Örtqvist Å, Blennow M, Carlsson R.M, Hanson LÅ, Lindberg A, Lindqvist L, et al. Vaccination of children – a systematic review (Original Article). *Foundation Acta Pædiatrica/Acta Pædiatrica* 2010; 99 (Suppl. 461):1–192.
- 116) Moffatt C. Public Health surveillance for Communicable Diseases in South Australia. *Public Health and Communicable Diseases. Public Health Bulletin South Australia* . 2006. Edition 4 /p.3.
- 117) Lambert PH. Research priorities for the WHO Global Program for Immunisation. *Dev Biol Stand*. 1996; 87:45-49.
- 118) World Health Organization, Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Annual Report of the Regional Director 1 January—31 December 2009, The Work of WHO in the Eastern Mediterranean Region World Health Organization 2010.
- 119) Connolly M, Gabrielli A.F, Gayer M (editors). Communicable Disease Profile, Iraq. World Health Organization Updated 19 March 2003.
- 120) World Health Organization – Iraq Office. Review report 2011.

- 121) Ameen M.H, Al Mosawi A.J, Anoze A. The Evolution of Modern Healthcare and Health Education In Iraq. The N Iraqi J Med, April 2011; 7(1):72-80.
- 122) World Health Organization, Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Iraq national health account 2008. World Health Organization 2011.WHO-EM/HEC/038/E.
- 123) Alwan A. Health in Iraq, The Current Situation, Our Vision for the Future and Areas of Work. Iraq. Ministry of Health, 2nd Edition, December 2004.
- 124) Webster P. Reconstruction efforts in Iraq failing health care. The lancet February 21, 2009; (Special Report)Vol.373:617-620.
- 125) World Health Organization, Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean, Iraq representative office. Stories that count 09. World Health Organization 2009.
- 126) Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Ministry of Health. Iraq Family Health Survey 2006/2007: In-Depth Report.
- 127) Iraq. Ministry of Health, Ministry of higher education, Ministry of planning / Center Statistical Office, Ministry of development, World Health Organization. Iraq Health Information System Review and Assessment July, 2011.
- 128) شعبة الرصد الوبائي، مركز السيطرة على الامراض الانتقالية. الرصد الوبائي: مفاهيم مبسطة حول الرصد الوبائي. وزارة الصحة العراقية. 2008.
- 129) Ibrahim R , Al Bar M. Surveillance of childhood vaccine preventable diseases at health facilities in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal. 2009; Vol.15.No.3:532-543.
- 130) Al-jawadi A.A, Al-neami M.A. Assessment of Infectious Diseases Surveillance System in Mosul, Iraq. Dohuk Medical Journal. 2008; Vol.2, No.1:127-138.

- 131) Assessment of infectious diseases surveillance –Uganda. 2000. Morbidity and mortality weekly report.2000; 49(30):687-91.
- 132) Ministry of Labor, Health and Social Affairs and National Center for Disease Control. Assessment of Vaccine Preventable Disease Surveillance Systems in Georgia. Technical Report No. 028. Bethesda, MD: The Partners for Health Reform plus Project, Abt Associates Inc. July 2002.
- 133) Miller M, Roche P, Spencer J, Deeble M. Evaluation of Australia's national notifiable disease surveillance system. *Commun Dis Intell*, 2004;28(3):311-23.
- 134) Sahal N, Reintjes R, Mahgoub AE, Aro AR. Assessment of core activities and supportive functions for the communicable diseases surveillance system in Khartoum state, Sudan, 2005–2007. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*. 2010;Vol. 16 No.12.
- 135) Wuhib T, Chorba TL, Davidiants V, MacKenzie WR, McNabb SN. Assessment of infectious diseases surveillance systems of the Republic of Armenia: an example of surveillance in the Republics of the former Soviet Union. *BMC Public Health* 2002;2(1):3-12.
- 136) Rushworth RL , Bell SM. Improving infectious disease surveillance in New South Wales. *Med J Aust* 1999;154(12):828-31.
- 137) World Health Organization, Department of Communicable Disease, Surveillance and Response, Regional Office for Africa. Guide for the Use of Core Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response Indicators in the African Region. July 2005.
- 138) Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Health. Communicable Diseases Control Guideline. CDCC Baghdad, 1999.
- 139) Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Health, Public health directorate, Immunization Department. Immunization Schedule for Iraq, 2011.

قرار لجنة المناقشة

نحن اعضاء لجنة المناقشة نشهد باننا قد اطلعنا على رسالة الماجستير التقني الموسومة: (تقييم فعاليات برنامج الرصد الوبائي للأمراض الانتقالية في مراكز الرعاية الصحية الاولية في محافظة بغداد) وناقشنا الطالب (جاسم ايمن خليفه) في محتوياتها وفيما له علاقة بها وفي ضوء ذلك وجد بأنه جدير بنيل درجة الماجستير التقني في اختصاص تقنيات صحة المجتمع.

التوقيع:

رئيس اللجنة: د. مازن غازي الربيعي

المرتبة العلمية: استاذ

التاريخ: ٢٠١٣/٤/٨

التوقيع:

عضو اللجنة: د. وفاء فائق توفيق

المرتبة العلمية: استاذ مساعد

التاريخ: ٢٠١٣/٤/٩

التوقيع:

عضو اللجنة: د. حسن مسلم عبدالحسين

المرتبة العلمية: استشاري صحة عامة

التاريخ: ٢٠١٣/٤/٩

التوقيع:

مشرفاً: د. سلاف احمد حسين

المرتبة العلمية: استاذ مساعد

التاريخ: ٢٠١٣/٤/٨

التوقيع:

الاسم: د. باقر كريم عبد

المرتبة العلمية: استاذ مساعد

عميد الكلية

التاريخ: ٢٠١٣/٤/٢٤

م/ اقرار المشرف

اني الاستاذ المساعد (د.سلاف احمد حسين) المشرف على رسالة طالب الماجستير التقني (جاسم ايمن خليفه) بموجب الامر الاداري المرقم (٥٤٧٠/٣) والمؤرخ (٢٩/١١/٢٠١١)، قد اطلعت على رسالة الطالب المذكور والذي انجزت تحت اشرافي، أقر وأؤيد صلاحيتها للمناقشة لاستيفائها كافة المتطلبات العلمية لنيل درجة الماجستير التقني.

التوقيع:
المشرف: د.سلاف احمد حسين
المرتبة العلمية: استاذ مساعد
التاريخ: ٢٠١٣ / ١٢ / ١٤

م/ اقرار المقوم اللغوي

إنني الاستاذ المساعد (د.سهى نعمان رشيد) المقوم اللغوي لرسالة طالب الماجستير التقني (جاسم ايمن خليفه) الموسومة (تقييم فعاليات برنامج الرصد الوبائي للأمراض الانتقالية في مراكز الرعاية الصحية الاولية في محافظة بغداد) أقر وأؤيد سلامتها اللغوية وصلاحيتها للمناقشة لاستيفائها كافة متطلبات هذا الجانب.

التوقيع:
المقوم اللغوي: د.سهى نعمان رشيد
المرتبة العلمية: استاذ مساعد
التاريخ: ٢٠١٣ / ١٢ / ١٤

م/ مصادقة

إنني رئيس قسم تقنيات صحة المجتمع في كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية، أصادق على إقرار المشرف على رسالة طالب الماجستير (جاسم ايمن خليفه) وعلى إقرار المقوم اللغوي، واعتبر الرسالة صالحة للمناقشة من قبل اللجنة الممتحنة المشكلة لهذا الغرض.

التوقيع:
الاسم: د. باسم موسى حسن
المرتبة العلمية: مدرس
رئيس قسم تقنيات صحة المجتمع
التاريخ: ٢٠١٣ / ٤ / ٢٤